

13TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
RELATIVISTIC EFFECTS IN HEAVY-
ELEMENT CHEMISTRY AND PHYSICS

REHE

20
22

BOOK OF ABSTRACT

From 26 September to 30 September 2022
BV Grand Hotel Assisi
Assisi, Italy

LOCAL ORGANIZATION

REHE 2022

Leonardo Belpassi - CNR-SCITEC Perugia, IT (chair)

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REHE 2020-2022

26-30 September 2022, Assisi, Italy

13th International Conference on Relativistic
Effects in Heavy-Element Chemistry and Physics

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REHE 2020-2022

26-30 September 2022, Assisi, Italy

13th International Conference on Relativistic
Effects in Heavy-Element Chemistry and Physics

EXTENDED LECTURES

REHE 2022

Christoph H. Keitel - MPIK, DE

Stephen T. Liddle - University of Manchester, UK

Victor V. Flambaum - UNSW Sydney, AU

Yuri T. Oganessian - FLNR, JINR, Dubna, RU

INVITED SPEAKERS

REHE 2022

Aleksandra A. Kiuberis - University of Groningen, NL

Alessandro Erba - University of Torino, IT

André Severo Pereira Gomes - CNRS-University of Lille, FR

Anastasia Borschevsky - University of Groningen, NL

Daniele Cesarini - CINECA, IT

Edit Mátyus - Eötvös Loránd University, HU

Ephraim Eliav - Tel Aviv University, IL

Gustavo A. Aucar - Northeastern National University, AR

Harry M. Quiney - The University of Melbourne, AU

Ilya Tupitsyn - St. Petersburg University

Ivano Tavernelli - IBM, CH

Jaideep Singh - Michigan State University, US

Joel Creutzberg - Lund University, SE

Kenneth G. Dyall - Dirac Solutions, US

Krzysztof Pachucki - University of Warsaw, PL

Lan Cheng - Johns Hopkins University, US

Lucas Visscher - Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, NL

Lukas Konecny - The Arctic University of Norway, NO

Maen Salman - CNRS - University Toulouse III, FR

INVITED SPEAKERS

REHE 2022

Marius Kadek - Northeastern University, US

Mauro Perfetti - University of Florence, IT

Michal Repisky - The Arctic University of Norway, NO

Minori Abe - Hiroshima University, JP

Mustapha Laatiaoui - JGU - HIM, DE

Paola Belanzoni - University of Perugia, IT

Paul Indelicato - LKB - CNRS, FR

Patrick Steinegger - ETHZ - PSI, CH

Peter A. Schwerdtfeger - Massey University Auckland, NZ

Robert Berger - University of Marburg, DE

Sang-Kil Son - CFEL - DESY, DE

Silvia Picozzi - CNR-SPIN, IT

Tonya Vitova - Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, DE

Trond Saue - CNRS - University Toulouse III, FR

Valeria Pershina - GSI Helmholtzzentrum für
Schwerionenforschung, DE

Vladimir Shabaev - St. Petersburg State University, RU

Volker Blum - Duke University, US

W. H. Eugen Schwarz - University of Siegen, DE

Wenjian Liu - Shandong University, CN

Xiaosong Li - University of Washington, US

CHAIRMEN

REHE 2022

Pekka Pyykkö - SESSION 01
Valeria Pershina - SESSION 02
Peter A. Schwerdtfeger - SESSION 03
Robert Berger - SESSION 04
Anastasia Borschevsky - SESSION 05
Alceo Macchioni - SESSION 06
Stephen T. Liddle - SESSION 07
Minori Abe - SESSION 08
Kenneth G. Dyall - SESSION 09
Xiaosong Li - SESSION 10
Filippo De Angelis - SESSION 11
Trond Saue - SESSION 12
Lucas Visscher - SESSION 13

PROGRAM

REHE 2022

DAY 1

SEPTEMBER 26

WELCOME AND REGISTRATION

From 14:30 to 18:00

OPENING CERIMONY

From 18:00 to 18:30

EXTENDED LECTURE SESSION 01

From 18:30 to 19:00

INVITED TALK SESSION 01

From 19:00 to 19:30

DINNER

From 19:30 to 21:00

HISTORICAL TALK

ABSTRACT

DAY 1
SEPTEMBER 26

PEKKA PYYKKÖ
"The road to Assisi"

The road to Assisi

Pekka Pyykkö

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The REHE programme of the ESF ran from 1992 to 1998 and the REHE symposia have been continued from De Haan, Belgium, in 1993 to REHE13 at Assisi, Italy, in 2022. Preceding REHE, about ten or more symposia or workshops were held in 1969-1990 in various places in Europe and North-America. That list may not be complete.

A theoretical basis is provided by the Dirac-Fock-Breit Hamiltonian, completed by some inclusion of QED. Taking the IP and EA of the gold atom as two test cases, the errors can be pressed down to meV level by going to CCSDTQP full Dirac +Breit +QED level. For molecular work, the lower levels with transformed Hamiltonians or pseudopotentials and, eventually, DFT provide cross-checks, that mutually agree.

Some applications will be listed and some possible future directions outlined.

EXTENDED LECTURE

ABSTRACT

DAY 1

SEPTEMBER 26

VICTOR V. FLAMBAUM

"Relativistic and QED effects in spectra and isotope shifts in superheavy atoms"

Relativistic and QED effects in spectra and isotope shifts in superheavy atoms

V.V. Flambaum^{1,2}, V.A. Dzuba¹, A. Geddes¹, A. Viatkina², B.J.C. Lackenby¹, J.C. Berengut¹

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Relativistic and QED effects play an important role in spectra and especially in isotope shifts (IS) in heavy and superheavy atoms. To account for the QED effects we derived formula for the radiative potential which reproduces the results of more rigorous QED calculations for one-electron (hydrogen-like) ions to the accuracy $\sim 1\%$ [1]. Advantage of our approach is that it allows one to include QED corrections into the Dirac-Hartree-Fock orbitals and accurately calculate radiative corrections to the energy levels and electromagnetic amplitudes in many electron atoms and molecules using standard many-body techniques.

Superheavy elements produced in laboratory are neutron-deficient and have short lifetimes. Calculations of the isotope shifts allows one to predict atomic spectra of more stable neutron rich elements belonging to a hypothetical island of stability using laboratory spectra of the neutron-deficient elements. These island of stability spectra may be searched in astrophysical data and future laboratory measurements. We derived formula for the field isotope shift suitable for superheavy elements which gives one analytical dependence on the nuclear charge and may be used to extrapolate IS from lighter elements to superheavy elements [2]. We also performed accurate numerical relativistic many-body calculations of atomic spectra and IS for the elements up to $Z=120$ and neutron number up to $N=184$ [3-5].

An interesting feature of isotope field shift in superheavy elements is that contrary to the lighter elements it is not sufficient to know the change of the r.m.s. nuclear radius between the isotopes. IS is actually sensitive to the details of the nuclear charge density distribution including nuclear deformation and depression of the charge density in the nuclear centre due to the proton repulsion [5] (nuclear charge density in some superheavy elements is predicted to have toroidal shape). This sensitivity is due to the rapid variation of the electron wave function inside superheavy nuclei (in light atoms electron wave function tends to constant and is not sensitive to the nuclear charge density details).

Another interesting property of the superheavy elements is that orbitals with different values of the electron angular momentum $j=l+1/2$ and $j=l-1/2$ form separate subshells and blur the features the shell structure [4].

High precision measurements and calculations of atomic spectra and King plot for IS are used to search for new elementary particles [2,6].

References

- [1] V. V. Flambaum and J. S. M. Ginges, Phys. Rev. A (2005) 72, 052115.
- [2] V.V. Flambaum, A. Geddes, A.V. Viatkina, Phys. Rev. A (2018) 97, 032510.
- [3] B.G.C. Lackenby, V.A. Dzuba, V.V. Flambaum, Phys. Rev. A (2019) 99, 042509.
- [4] B. G. C. Lackenby V. A. Dzuba, V. V. Flambaum, Phys. Rev. A(2018) 98, 042512.
- [5] V. V. Flambaum and V. A. Dzuba, Phys. Rev. A (2019) 100 , 032511.
- [6] J. C. Berengut, D. Budker, C. Delaunay, V. V. Flambaum, C. Fruguele et al, Phys. Rev. Lett. (2018) 120, 103202.

INVITED TALK

ABSTRACT

DAY 1
SEPTEMBER 26

W. H. EUGEN SCHWARZ

"REHE - Revolution of the Periodic Table at the Bottom"

REHE - Revolution of the Periodic Table at the Bottom

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When the first half-hundred chemical elements (mainly lighter ones) had been discovered, L.Gmelin *classified* them in groups, since the **1820s**, according to similarity of properties, from the alkali metals (**A**) to the halogens (**X**). *Ordering* them, around **1870**, in addition by nuclear mass (L.Meyer, Mendeleev; later by charge: Moseley), the periodicity of the (light) elements was disclosed, with property values such as valence-numbers increasing stepwise from **A** to **X**, and a large jump down from **X** to (Ng) to **A**. In **1920**, Bohr initiated the physical explanation of this saw-tooth behavior of properties by the orbital model. Educators of chemistry then extrapolated the structure of the periodic table from the lighter elements up to $Z > 100(0)$. In this non-relativistic light-atom view, the $7p$ elements were predicted as typical p-block ones, and the $8s$ elements as typical alkali/alkaline-earth ones.

In the early **1970s**, Fricke^[1] and others speculated on higher valences than 0,1,2 for the heavy elements of groups 0,1,2. Recently, Schwerdtfeger et al.^[2] showed that ‘noble gas Oganesson’ is neither noble nor a gas, but a solid semiconductor with chemically active $7p_{3/2}$ shell and a small band gap to $8s$. Meanwhile, unusual valences were predicted by various groups^[3] for the late $6d_{5/2}$, the $6d_{5/2}7s$, the $7s7p_{1/2}$ and the $7p_{3/2}$ elements 108 to 118.

In the **2020s**, we present single-configuration DFT and correlated WFT results for molecules of super-heavy s-block elements 119 and 120 and their lighter homologs. Already at the *non-relativistic level*, the periodicity-determining large orbital energy gap above the $n(sp)^8$ shell fades away! In addition, *relativistic* effects (kinematics, shielding, S-O coupling) change the chemical character of the heavy p-block elements,^[3] and even more so the heavy s-block elements. The latter are predicted as behaving like a new class of open p-shell elements, with rare bond-strengthening by spin-orbit coupling. We plead for abandoning the common non-realistic non-relativistic $(n+l, n)$ textbook rule. And we suggest the experimental synthesis of radium complexes in oxidation state +6.^[4]

References

- ^[1] B. Fricke, J.T. Waber, *Actin. Revs.* **1**, 433-485 (1971).
- ^[2] J.-M. Mewes, P. Jerabek, O.R. Smits, P. Schwerdtfeger, *Angew. Chem. IE* **58**, 14260-64 (2019); O.R. Smits, J.-M. Mewes, P. Jerabek, P. Schwerdtfeger, *Angew. Chem. IE* **59**, 23636-40 (2020); O. Smits, Ab-initio bulk properties of oganesson, REHE 2020/2022 Virtual Talks program (2021).
- ^[3] e.g. V. Pershina, *Nucl Phys A* 944, 578-613 (2015). L. Trombach, S. Ehlert, S. Grimme, P. Schwerdtfeger, J.-M. Mewes, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **21**, 18048-18058 (2019). R. T. Santiago, R. L. A. Haiduke, *Theor. Chem. Acc.* 139, 60 (2020). P. Schwerdtfeger, O. R. Smits, P. Pyykkö, *Nat. Rev. Chem.* **4**, 359-380 (2020). J.-M. Mewes, P. 60, 7703-7709 (2021). S.-X. Hu, W.-L. Zou, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 24, 321-325 (2021). S. Löffelsender, P. Schwerdtfeger, S. Grimme, J.-M. Mewes, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 144, 485-494 (2022). M.L. Terranova, O.A.P. Tavares, *Rend. Linc. Sci. Fis. Nat.* doi 10.1007/s12210-022-01057-w, 16 pp. (2022).
- ^[4] C.-S. Cao, H.-S.Hu, W.H.E. Schwarz, J. Li, “Periodic Law of Chemistry Overturms for Superheavy Elements”, submitted April (2022).

PROGRAM

REHE 2022

DAY 2

SEPTEMBER 27

EXTENDED LECTURE SESSION 02

From 09:00 to 09:30

INVITED TALKS SESSION 02

From 09:30 to 10:30

INVITED TALKS SESSION 03

From 11:00 to 12:30

INVITED TALKS SESSION 04

From 14:30 to 16:30

INVITED TALKS SESSION 05

From 17:00 to 19:30

COFFEE BREAKS

From 10:30 to 11:00

From 16:30 to 17:00

LUNCH

From 12:30 to 13:30

DINNER

From 19:30 to 21:00

POSTER SESSION - Odd numbers

From 21:00 to 23:00

EXTENDED LECTURE

ABSTRACT

DAY 2
SEPTEMBER 27

YURI OGANESSIAN

"Mass Limits of Nuclei and Elements"

Mass Limits for Nuclei and Elements.

Yuri Oganessian¹

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This “extended lecture” series is an introduction to the long-awaited REHE 2020/2022 conference. Since nuclear and electromagnetic forces are very different from each other, the limits of the existence of nuclei and atoms (elements) are also different for these substances. The discovery of new elements in the reactions of cold and hot fusion filled almost the entire 7th row of the Table from 104 to 118 elements. Leaving the "mainland of stability" at 208Pb and reaching the SHE islands, we observe the amazing survivability of atomic nuclei. The heaviest nucleus $A=294$, obtained twice as an isotope of 117 and 118 elements, turned out to be not at all limiting. The study of the electronic structure of super heavy atoms also seems promising. The relativistic contraction of the inner electron orbits of the SHE can definitely change the Periodic Table on the way to the critical charge $Z=173$. Changes in the chemical and macro physical properties of the smaller one will begin much earlier, already in the synthesized SHE. It seems to me that new approaches in theory and new experimental possibilities will ensure progress in this direction in the near future.

INVITED TALKS

ABSTRACT

DAY 2

SEPTEMBER 27

PATRICK STEINEGGER

"Prospects in experimental superheavy element chemistry"

JAIDEEP TAGGART SINGH

"Towards a Search for Time-Reversal Violation Using Pear-Shaped Nuclei Implanted in Cryogenic Solids"

MUSTAPHA LAATIAOUI

"Optical Spectroscopy of the Heaviest Elements"

ANASTASIA BORSCHEVSKY

"High accuracy calculations for heavy elements in support of experimental research"

VALERIA PERSHINA

"Predictions of Properties and Experimental Behaviour of Superheavy Elements"

PETER SCHWERDTFEGER

"Is flerovium behaving like a noble-gas element?"

EPHRAIM ELIAV

"Benchmark electronic structures calculations at the edge of Periodic Table"

INVITED TALKS

ABSTRACT

DAY 2

SEPTEMBER 27

VLADIMIR SHABAEV

"QED with heavy ions: on the way to supercritical fields"

PAUL INDELICATO

"Relativistic effects, QED corrections and correlation in heavy and super-heavy elements total binding energies"

TROND SAUE

"Does chemistry need more physics?"

EDIT MÁTYUS

"Relativistic and non-adiabatic developments for molecular quantum theory"

KRZYSZTOF PACHUCKI

"QED theory of the nuclear magnetic shielding"

GUSTAVO A. AUCAR

"Studying relativistic and QED effects on response properties with polarization propagators. Its application to NMR spectroscopic parameters"

ROBERT BERGER

"Radium monofluoride and the violation of fundamental symmetries"

Prospects in experimental superheavy element chemistry

Patrick Steinegger^{1,2}

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State-of-the-art gas-adsorption chromatography experiments have been successfully used for the chemical characterization of superheavy elements (SHEs) Sg, Hs, Cn and Fl. Despite ongoing discussions regarding the somewhat special case of flerovium among experimentalists and theoreticians alike, the focus has increasingly shifted towards nihonium. In this regard, accelerator-based experiments with short-lived radioisotopes of the lighter homolog thallium revealed unexpected observations. These highlight the importance of such preliminary, online studies with homologs of SHEs. Further challenges in future experiments with SHEs concern the short half-lives below the one second threshold of all radioisotopes of elements beyond flerovium as well as the general need for higher stationary surface temperatures in order to address also relatively less volatile chemical species.

Here, we present our future experimental plans regarding chemical research with SHEs at the Paul Scherrer Institute and the ETH Zurich together with our international partners. We will discuss already implemented or envisaged solutions for the above-mentioned challenges and highlight how a strong cooperation between theory and experiment can substantially further progress in this demanding field of fundamental science.

Towards a Search for Time-Reversal Violation Using Pear-Shaped Nuclei Implanted in Cryogenic Solids

Jaideep Taggart Singh¹

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Certain rare pear-shaped nuclei such as ²²⁵Ra and ²²⁹Pa may have unmatched sensitivity to new kinds of forces between subatomic particles that are not the same when the arrow of time is reversed [1]. Such forces are believed to be responsible for the near absence of antimatter in the observable Universe [2]. These rare isotopes, some for the first time, will be produced in sufficiently large quantities at the Facility for Rare Isotope Beams at Michigan State University providing an unprecedented opportunity to probe for new physics [3]. In anticipation, we intend to use stable elements such as Ba and Yb to develop new techniques to manipulate nuclei embedded inside an optically transparent solid at cryogenic temperatures [4,5]. Implantation into a solid, such as neon and argon, is potentially an effective way to both efficiently capture and repeatedly probe the small number of rare nuclei. An optically transparent host medium at cryogenic temperatures would allow for the laser manipulation of the nuclei in a thermally quiet and stable environment for a wide variety of guest species such as polar molecules. In such systems, the nuclei are exposed to extraordinarily large electric fields and magnetic field gradients, which significantly amplifies the measurability of certain time-reversal violating effects. The potential sensitivity of this new approach could be at least a few hundred times greater than the current leading experiment which uses mercury atoms. I will present on the present status of our experimental efforts.

[1] N. Auerbach, V.V. Flambaum, and V. Spevak, *Physical Review Letters* (1996), 76, 4316-4319.

[2] T.E. Chupp, P. Fierlinger, M.J. Ramsey-Musolf, and J.T. Singh, *Reviews of Modern Physics* (2019), 91, 015001.

[3] E.P. Abel et al., *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics* (2019), 46, 100501.

[4] A.C. Vutha, M. Horbatsch, and E.A. Hessels, *Physical Review A* (2018), 98, 032513.

[5] J.T. Singh, *Hyperfine Interactions* (2019), 240, 29.

Optical Spectroscopy of the Heaviest Elements

Mustapha Laatiaoui

Johannes Gutenberg-Universität, Mainz, Germany

Helmholtz-Institut Mainz, Mainz, Germany

In recent years, great progress was made in the study of the atomic and nuclear properties of the superheavy elements, driven by the need to understand the nuclear stability and chemical behavior of these atoms.

Optical spectroscopy enables the experimental study of the atomic structure of the elements and provides an alternative access to important nuclear properties such as spins, moments and changes in the mean square charge radii. In this respect, however, the superheavy elements are still unexplored territory. Even certain isotopes of fermium (Fm, $Z=100$), which can still be obtained in macroscopic quantities, pose a challenge for such studies, not to mention transfermium elements, which can only be produced at in-flight separator facilities.

Over the years, laser resonance ionisation spectroscopy has emerged as the method of choice for atomic level searches and subsequent hyperfine spectroscopy of the heaviest elements. The successful application of this method to the element nobelium (No, $Z=102$) has spurred efforts to study even heavier, more exotic radionuclides [1,2,3,4,5].

In this talk I will present results from recent spectroscopy of several nobelium and fermium isotopes, followed by a brief outlook on the spectroscopy of lawrencium (Lr, $Z=103$).

References

- [1] M. Laatiaoui et al., *Nature* **538**, 495 (2016).
- [2] P. Chhetri et al., *PRL* **120**, 263003 (2018).
- [3] S. Raeder et al., *PRL* **120**, 232503 (2018).
- [4] M. Laatiaoui et al., *PRL* **125**, 023002 (2020).
- [5] J. Warbinek et al., *Atoms* **10**, 41 (2022).

High accuracy calculations for heavy elements in support of experimental research.

Anastasia Borschevsky

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Atomic theory can provide important support at all the stages of spectroscopic experiments, from planning the measurements, through extracting the properties of interest from the data, and to the interpretation of the results and their comparison to theoretically predicted values. Such support is especially crucial in case of heavy and superheavy unstable elements, which are challenging for experiments due to the low quantities produced and the very short lifetimes. To this end, highly accurate calculations of atomic properties are needed; furthermore, one should be able to set uncertainties on the predicted properties. When dealing with heavy elements, in order to be reliable, such calculations must include both relativistic effects and electron correlation on the highest possible level.

Relativistic coupled cluster is considered one of the most powerful methods for investigations of properties of heavy elements. It is accurate and versatile, and can be used to treat atoms and molecules, systems of multireference character, and a variety of properties. Furthermore, this method has the advantage of the possibility to improve the calculation systematically, and to estimate the order of magnitude of the missing effects. Recently, we have developed a scheme for using a detailed computational study to estimate the uncertainties of the calculated values. We are thus able to provide our experimental colleagues with highly accurate and reliable predictions that can be directly used in planning and in interpreting their measurements.

A brief introduction to relativistic coupled cluster method will be provided, focusing on error estimates. In the remainder of the talk I will present recent successful applications of this method to spectra, hyperfine structure, and other properties of heavy elements in an experimental context.

Predictions of Properties and Experimental Behaviour of Superheavy Elements

Valeria Pershina

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Superheavy elements (SHEs) whose chemical properties are presently under experimental investigations are Nh ($Z=113$) and Fl ($Z=114$). The measurements are done using fast gas-phase chromatography separation techniques handling half-lives, $t_{1/2}$, of SHEs of 1 s and smaller.^{1,2} Recently, first experiments have been conducted with a ^{288}Mc ($Z=115$) isotope having $t_{1/2}=164_{-21}^{+30}$ ms.³ Further developments of the techniques should allow for detection of even shorter lived isotopes, with $t_{1/2}$ of a few ms.⁴ This opens prospects for chemical investigations of Lv ($Z=116$) and Ts ($Z=117$).

Theoretical predictions of chemical properties of SHEs are indispensable for sophisticated and demanding experiments with single atoms and extremely low statistics of events. They help design those experiments and interpret their outcome. Traditionally, we have been working on those topics in close relation to the experimental research.⁵ The investigations comprise a large number of chemical systems, from solid state to complexes in solutions and gas phase molecules. Beside consideration of atomic and molecular properties at the highest level of relativistic theory, such as e.g. the DIRAC software, we deal with adsorption of atoms and molecules of SHEs on surfaces of different materials using relativistic periodic codes. The latter research is directly related to the running gas-phase experiments on adsorption of SHEs and their homologs on surfaces of detectors of chromatography columns.^{6,7}

In the presentation, our recent results of the studies of gas phase properties and adsorption behavior of elements with $Z > 112$ and their compounds are overviewed. Influence of relativistic effects is discussed.

References

- [1] S. N. Dmitriev, *et al.*, *Mendeleev Commun.* (2014) **24**, 253.
- [2] A. Yakushev, R. Eichler, *EPJ Web of Conferences* (2016) **131**, 07003.
- [3] A. Yakushev, to be published.
- [4] V. Varentsov, A. Yakushev, *Nucl. Inst. Meth. Phys. Res.* (2019) **A940**, 20.
- [5] V. Pershina, *Radiochim. Acta* (2019) **107**, 833.
- [6] V. Pershina, *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.* (2021) **60**, 9796.
- [7] V. Pershina, M. Iliáš, *Dalton's Trans.* (2022) **51**, 7321.

Is flerovium behaving like a noble-gas element?

P. Schwerdtfeger¹, O. Smits¹, E. Florez,¹ L. Trombach,¹ J.-M. Mewes² and P. Jerabek³

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As early as 1975, Pitzer suggested that copernicium, flerovium and oganesson are volatile substances behaving noble-gas like because of their closed-shell configurations and accompanying relativistic effects [1]. Both copernicium and oganesson have been analyzed very recently by our group [2]. They are predicted to be semi-conductors and volatile substances with rather low melting and boiling points, which may justify a comparison with the noble gas elements. Flerovium (Fl) exhibits a closed-shell $7p_{1/2}$ configuration due to the strong spin-orbit stabilisation of the shell, causing a dramatic reduction in reactivity compared to its lighter congener Pb. This is reflected in the calculated adsorption energy on a gold surface (0.7 eV using density functional theory), compared to 2.8 eV for lead [3]. The volatility of Fl has been determined experimentally to be closer to Hg [4], which is consistent with the calculated adsorption energies of 0.78 eV (Hg) and 0.75 eV (Fl). Furthermore, GW calculations for the electronic band gap of bulk flerovium suggests that it is a semi-conductor similar to copernicium [1]. Furthermore, unlike the lighter noble gases, the many-body decomposition of the cohesive energy is not converging smoothly, Figure 1, in line with Hg. First predictions from Monte-Carlo simulation estimates the melting point at 290 ± 35 K.

Figure 1. Many-body decomposition of the cohesive energy for flerovium.

References

- [1] K. S. Pitzer, *J. Chem. Phys.* (1975), 63, 1032-1033.
- [2] J.-M. Mewes, O. R. Smits, G. Kresse, P. Schwerdtfeger, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* (2019), 58, 17964-17968; A O. Smits, J.-M. Mewes, P. Jerabek, P. Schwerdtfeger, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* (2020), 59, 23636-23640; J.-M. Mewes, P. Schwerdtfeger, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* (2021), 60, 7703-7709; J.-M. Mewes, P. Jerabek, O. R. Smits, P. Schwerdtfeger, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* (2019), 58, 14260-14264.
- [3] L. Trombach, S. Ehlert, S. Grimme, P. Schwerdtfeger, J.-M. Mewes, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* (2019), 21, 18048-18058.
- [4] R. Eichler, N. V. Aksenov, Y. V. Albin, A. V. Belozarov, G. A. Bozhikov, et al., *Radiochim. Acta* (2010), 98, 133-139.

Benchmark electronic structures calculations at the edge of Periodic Table

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High-accuracy calculations of atomic properties of the heaviest elements, are reviewed (for more details see [1]). The properties discussed include electronic structure and energetics (ionization potentials, electron affinities, excitation energies), which are associated with the spectroscopic and chemical behavior of these elements and are therefore of considerable interest. Accurate predictions of these quantities require high order inclusion of relativity, QED and electron correlation effects, as well as large, converged basis sets. The Dirac-Coulomb-Breit Hamiltonian, which includes all terms up to second order in the fine-structure constant, serves as the framework for the treatment; higher-order Lamb shift terms are considered in selected cases. Electron correlation is treated by the Fock-space coupled cluster method, enhanced by the intermediate Hamiltonian scheme, allowing the use of large, converged model (P) spaces.

The calculations on superheavy elements (SHE) are supported by the very good agreement with experiment obtained for the lighter homologues, usually within a few hundredths of an eV, and similar accuracy is expected for the SHEs, with $Z > 100$, for which experimental values are scarce. Many of the properties predicted for these species differ significantly from what may be expected by straightforward extrapolation of lighter homologs, demonstrating that the structure and chemistry of SHEs are strongly affected by relativity and electron correlation.

The major scientific challenge of the calculations is to find the electronic structure and basic atomic properties of the SHE and assign its proper place in the periodic table. The extended Periodic Table up to E174 is presented on the base of our benchmark calculations. Different unusual inclinations and irregularities of the Periodic Law at the edge of extended Periodic System are discussed.

References

- [1] E. Eliav, A.Borschevsky, U.Kaldor, in "Handbook of Relativistic Quantum Chemistry", Ed. W. Liu 2015, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, chapter

QED with heavy ions: on the way to supercritical fields

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The current status of tests of quantum electrodynamics (QED) with heavy ions is briefly reviewed. Special attention is focused on tests of QED in supercritical regime. It is known that in slow collisions of two bare nuclei with the total charge number larger than the critical value, $Z_1+Z_2 > Z_c = 173$, the initially neutral vacuum can spontaneously decay into the charged vacuum and two positrons. Detection of the spontaneous emission of positrons would be the direct evidence of this fundamental phenomenon. However, the spontaneous positron emission is generally masked by the dynamical positron emission, which is induced by a strong time-dependent electric field created by the colliding nuclei. For many years it was believed that the vacuum decay can be observed only in collisions with nuclear sticking, when the nuclei are bound for some period of time due to nuclear forces. But to date there is no evidence for the nuclear sticking in such heavy-ion collisions. In our recent papers [1,2], it was shown that the vacuum decay can be observed without any sticking of the nuclei. This can be done via measurements of the pair-production probabilities or the positron spectra for a given set of nuclear trajectories. The results of this study will be presented in the talk.

References

- [1] I.A. Maltsev, V.M. Shabaev, R.V. Popov, Y.S. Kozhedub, G. Plunien, X. Ma, and Th. Stöhlker, and D.A. Tumakov, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* (2019), 123 , 113401.
- [2] R.V. Popov, V.M. Shabaev, D.A. Telnov, I.I. Tupitsyn, I.A. Maltsev, Y.S. Kozhedub, A.I. Bondarev, N.V. Kozin, X. Ma, G. Plunien, Th. Stöhlker, D.A. Tumakov, and V.A. Zaytsev, *Phys. Rev. D* (2020), 102, 076005.

Relativistic effects, QED corrections and correlation in heavy and super-heavy elements total binding energies

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Accurate electronic binding energies are required in many fields of physics and physical chemistry. When moving to high- Z systems, relativistic effects bound-state quantum-electrodynamics corrections become very important. They can change the level order in many elements, leading to a change of the structure of the ground state and to the appearance of very long-lived metastable levels. Recently the accurate knowledge of binding energies to better than 1 eV became an issue to obtain atomic masses from high-precision measurements in highly charged ions [1,2]. The level orders can drastically change for highly charged ions due to relativistic effects. In some cases, metastable states with very long lifetime can appear, as was shown a long time ago for Ti-like ions [3] and hyperfine quenching can then play a very important role [4]. Such a long lived state, hyperfine-quenched (lifetime ~ 130 day), was observed recently in $^{187}\text{Re}^{73+}$ Pd-like ions using high-precision mass spectrometry [5]. Such long-lived states can be excellent candidates for high-precision atomic clocks [6].

We have performed an extensive systematic study of atomic binding energies for many different configurations for atoms and ions with up to 118 electrons to identify the ground state and possible long lived metastable states. We have performed Dirac-Fock calculations, for atomic numbers up to $Z=170$, to identify with certainty the right ground configuration. Improved bound-state quantum-electrodynamics corrections have been added using recent all-order self-energy corrections that take into account finite nuclear size for ns and $np_{1/2}$ states with $1 \leq Z \leq 6$ [7] and which have been extended to all value of n , l up to $n=10$, $l=9$ [8]. Examples of the effect of correlation will be presented.

References

- [1] P. Filianin *et al.*, Phys. Rev. Lett. **127**, 072502 (2021).
- [2] A. Rischka *et al.*, Phys. Rev. Lett. **124**, 113001 (2020).
- [3] U. Feldman, J. Sugar, and P. Indelicato, J. Opt. Soc. of Am. B **8**, 3 (1990).
- [4] F. Parente, J. P. Marques, and P. Indelicato, EPL **26**, 437 (1994).
- [5] R. X. Schüssler *et al.*, Nature **581**, 42 (2020).
- [6] M. G. Kozlov, M. S. Safronova, J. R. Crespo López-Urrutia, and P. O. Schmidt, Rev. Mod. Phys. **90**, 045005 (2018).
- [7] P. Indelicato and P. J. Mohr, in *to be published* (2022).
- [8] P. Indelicato, U. Jentschura, and P. J. Mohr, in *to be published* (2022).

Does chemistry need more physics ?

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The building blocks of chemistry are organized in the periodic table, which requires quantum mechanics for its understanding. In the 1980s it was realized that in order to correctly describe the heavy elements in the lower part of the periodic table, the special theory of relativity had to be invoked. With increasing accuracy of relativistic molecular calculations, one may ask if further physics needs to be introduced.

Is the vacuum really empty ?

An ideal situation for accurate calculations is a molecule alone in space at 0K. However, is the vacuum really empty ? It has been shown that placing a molecule in an otherwise empty cavity will change its reactivity [1]. This is explained by the coupling of the molecule to the zero-point vibrations of the quantized electromagnetic field.

Presently, we are particularly interested in the effects leading to the Lamb shift, a splitting between the $2S_{1/2}$ and $2P_{1/2}$ -levels of one-electron atoms, not predicted by the Dirac equation, but observed for the first time in 1947 by Lamb and Retherford.

Vacuum polarization: A charge in space is surrounded by virtual electron-positron pairs. This will contribute to the observed charge.

Electron self-energy: A charge drags along its electromagnetic field. This will contribute to the observed mass.

The splitting is a mere 4 meV, but for hydrogen-like uranium the splitting has grown to an impressive 468 eV. It is therefore legitimate to ask if QED-effects could play a role in the chemistry of heavy elements. In my contribution I will report on the implementation of effective QED potentials in the DIRAC code [2] and report sample calculations[3].

References

- [1] James A. Hutchison, Tal Schwartz, Cyriaque Genet, Eloïse Devaux, and Thomas W. Ebbesen. Modifying Chemical Landscapes by Coupling to Vacuum Fields. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 51(7):1592–1596, 2012.
- [2] Trond Saue, Radovan Bast, André Severo Pereira Gomes, Hans Jørgen Aa. Jensen, Lucas Visscher, Ignacio Agustín Aucar, Roberto Di Remigio, Kenneth G. Dyall, Ephraim Eliav, Elke Fasshauer, Timo Fleig, Loïc Halbert, Erik Donovan Hedegård, Benjamin Helmich-Paris, Miroslav Iliaš, Christoph R. Jacob, Stefan Knecht, Jon K. Laerdahl, Marta L. Vidal, Malaya K. Nayak, Małgorzata Olejniczak, Jørgvan Magnus Haugaard Olsen, Markus Pernpointner, Bruno Senjean, Avijit Shee, Ayaki Sunaga, and Joost N. P. van Stralen. The DIRAC code for relativistic molecular calculations. *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 152(20):204104, 2020.
- [3] Ayaki Sunaga, Maen Salman, and Trond Saue. 4-component relativistic Hamiltonian with effective QED Potentials for molecular calculations. submitted, 2022.

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Relativistic and non-adiabatic developments for molecular quantum theory

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High and ultra-high precision spectroscopy experiments of small molecular systems make it possible to test and further develop the fundamental theory of molecular matter. The molecular and atomic range of matter is governed by quantum mechanics and the interaction of the constituent particles, the electrons and the atomic nuclei, is dominated by electromagnetic interactions. Although the Lagrangian density of relativistic quantum electrodynamics (QED) is standard textbook material, it is a non-trivial task to write down the most possible complete wave equation (that fulfills basic requirements, like Lorentz invariance) and that could be solved (numerically) to high precision. To compute bound and quasi-bound molecular states, series approximations have been traditionally evoked in terms of the small parameters of the theory: the electron-to-proton mass ratio, $(m_e/m_p)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, the fine-structure constant, α , and its nuclear-charge-number multiple, $Z\alpha$. The series expansions of the relativistic QED description of few-body systems lead to the fundamental concepts currently in use, *e.g.*, the non-relativistic and the Born–Oppenheimer approximations to describe the structure and dynamics of molecular systems. Furthermore, the series expansions result in a number of ‘effects’ that needs to be accounted for by perturbation theory, if a quantitative theory-experiment agreement is sought for. Comparison with experiments of high energy resolution shows that the ‘small’ effects often ignored (or approximated) are ‘visible’ and important, their partial cancellation cannot be predicted *a priori*, moreover, the relative magnitude of the corrections changes from system to system and from transition to transition. Although the perturbative non-adiabatic and relativistic approaches support our current intuitive picture of molecular processes at low orders, the higher-order corrections, necessary for a quantitative agreement with the most precise experiments, become increasingly complicated (formally and numerically) and are always limited to some finite order. For this reason, I will speak about complementary perturbative [1, 2] and variational [3, 4, 5, 6] approaches to the non-adiabatic and relativistic problems of molecular quantum theory. I will sketch theoretical, algorithmic, and computational challenges that were recently met and that are still open for small atomic and molecular systems in relation with (ultra-)high-resolution spectroscopy experiments.

References

- [1] E. Mátyus and S. Teufel, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2019), 151, 014113. [arXiv](#)
- [2] D. Ferenc, V. I. Korobov and E. Mátyus, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* (2020), 125, 213001. [arXiv](#)
- [3] E. Mátyus, *Mol. Phys.* (2019), 117, 590. [arXiv](#)
- [4] P. Jeszenszki, D. Ferenc and E. Mátyus, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2021), 154, 224110. [arXiv](#)
- [5] P. Jeszenszki, D. Ferenc and E. Mátyus, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2022), 156, 084111. [arXiv](#)
- [6] D. Ferenc, P. Jeszenszki and E. Mátyus, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2022), 156, 084110. [arXiv](#)

QED theory of the nuclear magnetic shielding

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I will describe the quantum electrodynamic theory of the nuclear magnetic shielding in light atomic and molecular systems, and accurate determination of nuclear magnetic moments from the NMR spectroscopy [1,2].

References

- [1] M. Puchalski, J. Komasa, A. Spyszkiwicz, and K. Pachucki, Phys. Rev. A **105**, 042802 (2022)
- [2] D. Wehrli, M. Puchalski, and K. Pachucki, Phys. Rev. A **105**, 032808 (2022)
- [3] D. Wehrli, A. Spyszkiwicz-Kaczmarek, M. Puchalski, and K. Pachucki, Phys. Rev. Lett. **127**, 263001 (2021)

Studying relativistic and QED effects on response properties with polarization propagators. Its application to NMR spectroscopic parameters

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Polarization propagators are one of the few theoretical tools that are under continuous development to studying atomic and molecular response properties within a relativistic framework [1]. Recently it was found that those propagators can be derived from an appropriate generating functional which is defined making use of the path integral formalism [2]. Furthermore, given that there are some equivalences among the Feynman propagators and the polarization propagators, one can use well-known theoretical tools of high-energy physics in low-energy physics.

In this presentation I shall first sketch about the theoretical grounds by which one can introduce both, relativistic and QED effects within the formalism of polarization propagators. Then, the main part of it will treat about some recently developed models to estimate the order of magnitude of those effects on two of the NMR spectroscopic parameters, the nuclear magnetic shieldings and the indirect J-couplings [3, 4].

References

- [1] "Calculation of NMR and EPR Parameters. Theory and Applications". Ed. M. Kaupp, M. Bühl and V. G. Malkin. Chapters 13-15. Wiley-VCH. 2004; "Relativistic theories of NMR shieldings". Y. Xiao, W. Liu and J. Autschbach. Chap 21. Handbook of Relativistic Quantum Chemistry. Ed. W. Liu. Springer-Verlag. 2017.
- [2] G. A. Aucar, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* (2014), **16**, 4420-4438.
- [3] K. Koziol, I. A. Aucar and G. A. Aucar, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2019), **150**, 184301-14.
- [4] M. T. Colombo Jofré, K. Koziol, I. A. Aucar, K. Gaul, R. Berger and G. A. Aucar, *J. Chem. Phys.* Submitted.

Radium monofluoride and the violation of fundamental symmetries

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Radium monofluoride (RaF) was successfully proposed *ab initio* as a molecular candidate for laser-cooling [1]. This heavy-elemental radioactive compound features favourable characteristics for a measurement of the parity (P) violating nuclear anapole moment [2-4], the parity- and time-reversal (P,T) symmetry violating electron electric dipole moment [3-5] and other P,T-violating effects [3-7] that include also P,T-violation in the quark sector [7].

In this talk, I will discuss peculiarities of the electronic structure in RaF, the influences of P- and P,T-violating interactions, their scaling laws and relativistic enhancement factors, the prospects for disentangling different P,T-odd contributions as well as the role of quantum chemical calculations in recent [8,9] and future spectroscopic experiments on this intriguing diatomic molecule.

References

- [1] T.A. Isaev, S. Hoekstra and R. Berger, *Phys. Rev. A* (2010), 82, 052521.
- [2] T.A. Isaev and R. Berger, *Phys. Rev. A* (2012), 86, 062515.
- [3] T.A. Isaev and R. Berger, *arXiv:1302.5682* (2013).
- [4] A.D. Kudashov, A.N. Petrov, L.V. Skripnikov, N.S. Mosyagin, T.A. Isaev, R. Berger and A.V. Titov, *Phys. Rev. A* (2014), 90, 052513.
- [5] K. Gaul and R. Berger, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2017), 147, 014109.
- [6] K. Gaul, S. Marquardt, T. Isaev and R. Berger, *Phys. Rev. A* (2019), 99, 032509.
- [7] K. Gaul and R. Berger, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2020), 152, 044101.
- [8] R.F. Garcia Ruiz, R. Berger, J. Billowes, C.L. Binnersley, M.L. Bissell, A.A. Breier, A.J. Brinson, K. Chrysalidis, T. Cocolios, B. Cooper, K.T. Flanagan, T.F. Giesen, R.P. de Groote, S. Franchoo, F.P. Gustafsson, T.A. Isaev, A. Koszorús, G. Neyens, H.A. Perrett, C.M. Ricketts, S. Rothe, L. Schweikhard, A.R. Vernon, K. Wendt, F. Wienholtz, S.G. Wilkins, X.F. Yang, *Nature* (2020), 581, 396.
- [9] S.M. Udrescu, A.J. Brinson, R.F. Garcia Ruiz, K. Gaul, R. Berger, J. Billowes, C.L. Binnersley, M.L. Bissell, A.A. Breier, K. Chrysalidis, T.E. Cocolios, B.S. Cooper, K.T. Flanagan, Flanagan, T.F. Giesen, R.P. de Groote, S. Franchoo, F.P. Gustafsson, T.A. Isaev, A. Koszorús, G. Neyens, H.A. Perrett, C.M. Ricketts, S. Rothe, A.R. Vernon, K.D.A. Wendt, F. Wienholtz, S.G. Wilkins, X.F. Yang, *Phys. Rev. Lett* (2021), 127, 033001.

POSTER SESSION ODD NUMBERS

ABSTRACT

DAY 2

SEPTEMBER 27

CARSTEN ZÜLCH

"Molecular Ions for Fundamental Physics: A Systematic Investigation Throughout the Periodic Table of Elements"

DÁVID FERENC

"Towards an all-order explicitly correlated approach for precision spectroscopy"

E. EDUARDUS

"Towards Detection of Molecular Parity Violation in Helical Ferrocene, Ruthenocene, and Osmocene"

JACEK RZADKIEWICZ

"Ionization energies of W^{2+} through W^{27+} "

JOHANN VALENTIN POTOTSCHNIG

"Chemical insight from an improved Dailey-Townes model of nuclear quadrupole coupling"

KAROL KOZIOŁ

"Low-lying energy levels of Th^{39+} "

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"Highly-charged actinide molecules: A versatile laboratory to study fundamental physics"

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ABSTRACT

DAY 2

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LUCA GREGORI

"Host-Dopant Dative Bonding Facilitates Molecular Doping in Tin-Lead Perovskites"

MARIANO T. COLOMBO JOFRÉ

"Relativistic and QED corrections to one-bond indirect nuclear spin-spin couplings in X^{22+} and X^{32+} ions ($X = \text{Zn, Cd, Hg}$)"

MARTIN VAN HORN

"The validity of the electric dipole approximation in X-ray spectroscopy"

MICHIKO ATSUMI

"Compared non-relativistic effects and relativistic effects on $M2$ ($M = \text{Nh, Fl, Mc, Lv, Ts, and Og}$)"

PÉTER JESZENSZKI

"Variational Dirac-Coulomb approach with explicitly correlated basis functions"

TORSHA MOITRA

"Developing theoretical beamlines for ultrafast spectroscopy"

YANGYANG GUO

"High accuracy calculations of electron affinity of heavy and superheavy elements"

Molecular Ions for Fundamental Physics: A Systematic Investigation Throughout the Periodic Table of Elements

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Fundamental physics research continuously challenges experiment and theory, demanding a close cooperation of scientists from different areas of interest. One key challenge is finding suitable systems with large enhancements of e.g. \mathcal{P} , \mathcal{T} -odd effects, that are easy to produce, simple to handle and, preferable, contain optical cycling centers for laser-cooling. Polar molecules with large internal fields can exhibit orders of magnitude larger enhancements than atoms [1,2], but, evidently, impose additional difficulties, such as the need of molecular instead of atomic theory or of an analysis of congested rovibrational spectra. Ions have the experimental advantage that they can be guided by electric fields and sympathetically cooled [3] with long trapping times (seen in e.g. HfF^+ [4]) which might open up a path for subsequent direct laser-cooling of well chosen systems. Further, with increasing charge, relativistic effects become more dominant and electronic spectra become typically compressed, which is favourable for the search for variation of fundamental constants [5].

In this contribution we will discuss trends in the enhancement of various properties relevant for tests of fundamental physics of simple diatomic, molecular ions with the focus on molecules with a doublet ground state.

Electronic structures of the molecules are computed on the level of two-component complex generalized Hartree-Fock (cGHF) and Kohn-Sham (cGKS) within the zeroth order regular approximation (ZORA) and molecular properties are predicted subsequently with our toolbox approach described in Ref. [6]. Excited states are obtained using the maximum overlap approach allowing the computation of properties for all states in a self-consistent manner.

References

- [1] D. DeMille, *Physics Today* (2015), 68, 34.
- [2] V. Andreev et al., *Nature* (2018), 562, 355.
- [3] P. Rowe et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* (1999), 82, 2071.
- [4] W. B. Cairncross et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* (2017), 119, 153001.
- [5] J.-P. Uzan, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* (2003), 81, 403.
- [6] K. Gaul and R. Berger, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2020), 152, 044101.

Towards an all-order explicitly correlated approach for precision spectroscopy

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High-precision molecular spectroscopy experiments together with theoretical computations are proposed as tests of our fundamental understanding of ordinary matter in the low-energy range. The non-relativistic QED (nrQED) framework allows us to include higher-order relativistic and radiative processes as corrections to the Schrödinger equation. In this contribution, applications of nrQED is presented for the rovibrational intervals in the $EF\ ^1\Sigma_g^+$ excited electronic state of the hydrogen molecule and the rovibrational intervals of the $^4\text{He}_2^+$ molecular ion in its ground electronic state [1, 2]. In both cases the agreement of the experimental transitions with the latest theoretical results was for reduced by several orders of magnitude [3, 4]. The different contributions from the non-adiabatic, relativistic and QED corrections reveal an interesting interplay of the underlying physical phenomena.

Despite the excellent agreement for low Z molecules there is still room for improvement on the theoretical side. The nrQED fails for molecules with medium and high nuclear charge, and the computation of higher-order correction terms is an increasingly complex numerical task. An alternative approach could be formulated by the solution of the Dirac–Coulomb equation by treating the relativistic and correlation effects on an equal footing [5, 6]. The Breit interaction is considered for the first time in a variational explicitly correlated framework [7, 8]. Advances towards the full account of retardation are discussed.

- [1] D. Ferenc and E. Mátyus, *Phys. Rev. A* (2019), 100, 020501(R). [arXiv](#)
- [2] D. Ferenc, V. I. Korobov and E. Mátyus, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* (2020), 125, 213001. [arXiv](#)
- [3] L. Semeria, P. Jansen, G. Camenisch, F. Mellini, H. Schmutz and F. Merkt, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* (2020), 124, 213001.
- [4] G. D. Dickenson, E. J. Salumbides, M. Niu, Ch. Jungen, S. C. Ross and W. Ubachs, *Phys. Rev. A* (2012), 86, 032502.
- [5] P. Jeszenszki, D. Ferenc and E. Mátyus, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2021), 154, 224110. [arXiv](#)
- [6] P. Jeszenszki, D. Ferenc and E. Mátyus, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2022), 156, 084111. [arXiv](#)
- [7] D. Ferenc, P. Jeszenszki and E. Mátyus, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2022), 156, 084110. [arXiv](#)
- [8] D. Ferenc, P. Jeszenszki and E. Mátyus, (2022), in preparation

Towards Detection of Molecular Parity Violation in Helical Ferrocene, Ruthenocene, and Osmocene

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Naturally, most biological molecules are observed to have an absolute predominance of one enantiomeric form, called biohomochirality [1]. This phenomenon can be caused by a tiny difference in energy between the two enantiomers which is called parity violating (PV) energy difference. Astonishingly, although this symmetry-breaking effect in molecules has a firm theoretical basis, it has never been observed experimentally [2]. Scientists working at the Laboratoire de physique des lasers (LPL) in Paris are trying to measure the energy differences in vibrational spectra using the state-of-the-art laser within the mid-IR range and 100 mHz detection limit [3]. In this work, helical ferrocene, ruthenocene, and osmocene were studied theoretically, with the aim of predicting the size of the expected measurable parity violating effects. This work was carried out in 3 main steps: first, geometry optimization using Q-Chem to get the most stable structures and spin states. Second, relativistic single point energy calculations using DIRAC16 to get the vibrational and the parity violating energy curves. Last, the parity violating vibrational frequency shift was calculated using the Numerov-Cooley procedure. The result shows that ruthenocene and osmocene have promising structural stability in the gas phase. The most promising result from this work is the symmetrical ring breathing vibration of helical osmocene predicted to have a 3 Hz frequency shift, which is 30 times higher than the experimental target. Furthermore, generally, we find that the type of vibration plays a more important role in the sensitivity to the PV effects compared to the connected C atom displacement. However, the reason behind this sensitivity still left to be an open question.

References

- [1] W.A. Boner, *Chirality* (2000), 12, 114-126.
- [2] R. Berger, J. Stohner, *WIREs Comput. Mol. Sci.* (2019), 9, e1396.
- [3] A. Cournol and et al., *Quantum Electronics* (2019), 49, 288–292.

Ionization energies of W^{2+} through W^{27+}

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Tungsten, with its high melting point, high thermal resistance, low erosion rate, and low tritium retention, has been chosen as the plasma-facing material for the divertor of ITER thermonuclear reactor. Despite the low erosion rate, tungsten ions will appear in the plasma. Atomic data of low-charged and medium-charged tungsten ions are of growing interest in tokamak plasma diagnostics, especially for the ITER device [1]. The GRASP2018 code [2], implementing the multiconfiguration Dirac–Hartree–Fock method with configuration interaction, and the FAC code [3] have been used to calculate the ionization energies of W^{2+} through W^{27+} ions. The presented values have been made in order to examine the numbers provided by Kramida and Reader [4] and by Beiersdorfer et al. [5]. The influence of electron correlation on the W ionization energies is discussed, following the discussion initiated in our last paper [6].

Table 1. Present calculated IP for selected tungsten charge states, compared to the numbers found in the literature.

Charge state	GRASP	GRASP + CI	FAC	Ref. [4]	Ref. [5]
8+	158.53	160.11	157.58	160.2 ± 1.2	156.13
26+	831.03	831.37	830.91	833.4 ± 1.9	825.61

- [1] J. Clementson et al., *J. Phys. B At. Mol. Opt. Phys.* 43, 144009 (2010).
- [2] C. Froese Fischer et al., *Comput. Phys. Commun.* 237, 184 (2019).
- [3] M. F. Gu, *Can. J. Phys.* 86, 675 (2008).
- [4] A. E. Kramida and J. Reader, *At. Data Nucl. Data Tables* 92, 457 (2006).
- [5] P. Beiersdorfer et al., *High Energy Density Phys.* 8, 271 (2012).
- [6] K. Koziół and J. Rządkiwicz, *At. Data Nucl. Data Tables* 137, 101372 (2021).

Chemical insight from an improved Dailey–Townes model of nuclear quadrupole coupling

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Nuclei with a spin larger than $\frac{1}{2}$ can have a nuclear quadrupole moment which couples to the gradient of the electric field (EFG), the resulting energy levels can be measured using radio frequency. This allows to retrieve information about the electronic structure of the molecule via the electric field gradient, or, if the electronic structure is known, about the nuclear quadrupole moment. Dailey and Townes devised a simple model[1] to study the contributions to the electric field gradient in terms of ionic character and hybridization of the bond, only considering p-orbitals located on the center of interest contributing to the EFG.

In the current work the electric field gradient will be studied in combination with projection analysis, which was used to investigate bonding orbitals[2]. In contrast to the Dailey-Townes theory[1], which only considers the valence orbitals located on the center of interest, the contributions of different centers can be studied. The two approaches will be compared using relativistic Hamiltonians.

Figure 1: Electric field gradient within a diatomic molecule

References

- [1] C. H. Townes, B. P. Dailey. *J. Chem. Phys.* (1949), 17, 782-796
- [2] S. Dubillard, J.-B. Rota, T. Saue, K. Faegri. *J. Chem. Phys.* (2006), 124, 154307

Low-lying energy levels of Th^{39+}

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There is a strong interdisciplinary interest for ^{229}Th arising from its possible applications, such as nuclear clock frequency standard and precise determination of the temporal variation of fundamental constants, because its metastable first excited state, ^{229m}Th , is just ~ 8 eV above the nuclear ground state. Recently, the possibility of the electronic bridge excitation (EBE) of the ^{229m}Th isomer was investigated theoretically for Th^{35+} ion [1]. In the present work, the low-lying atomic levels of the Th^{39+} thorium ion, according to the $[\text{Kr}]4d^{10}4f^5$ electronic configuration, have been studied theoretically, employing the multiconfiguration Dirac–Hartree–Fock method with configuration interaction [2]. The promising transition $E \simeq 8.2$ eV, that may be useful in the EBE of the ^{229m}Th isomer, has been found.

Figure 1. Energy level diagram of Th^{39+} .

[1] P. V. Bilous et al., Phys. Rev. Lett. 124, 1 (2020).

[2] C. Froese Fischer et al., Comput. Phys. Commun. 237, 184 (2019).

**Highly-charged actinide molecules:
A versatile laboratory to study fundamental physics**

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Atomic highly charged ions have several favorable properties, such as large relativistic effects or compressed level structures and, thus, are prospective systems for the development of better clocks, tests of quantum electrodynamics or the search for new physics [1]. Moreover, precision spectroscopy of polar molecules provides some of the most stringent test of fundamental symmetry violations due to enormous enhancement by the large internal fields [2,3]. Thus, polar molecular highly charged ions would have the potential to combine the advantages of both systems.

In this contribution we discuss polar, highly charged molecules as prospective systems for high-precision spectroscopy and the search for new physics. Although a high charge dramatically weakens chemical bonding and drives systems to the edge of Coulomb explosion, multiply-charged actinide molecules can be thermodynamically stable. In particular we will discuss the stability, coolability and suitability for precision spectroscopy of the highly charged molecule PaF³⁺ [4]. With our versatile approach [5] to compute molecular properties within the quasi-relativistic zeroth order regular approximation (ZORA) we study the sensitivity of PaF³⁺ to different signatures of new physics in molecular spectra.

References

- [1] M. G. Kozlov, M. S. Safronova, J. R. Crespo López-Urrutia and P. O. Schmidt, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* (2018), 90, 045005.
- [2] D. DeMille, *Physics Today* (2015), 68, 34.
- [3] V. Andreev et al., *Nature* (2018), 562, 355.
- [4] C. Zülch, K. Gaul, S. M. Giesen, R. F. Garcia Ruiz and R. Berger, *arXiv* (2022), physics.chem-ph, 2203.10333.
- [5] K. Gaul and R. Berger, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2020), 152, 044101.

Host-Dopant Dative Bonding Facilitates Molecular Doping in Tin-Lead Perovskites

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Electrical doping stands as an effective pathway to attain strict control over the electronic properties of hybrid perovskite materials^[1], which is crucial to ensure their optimal implementation into next-generation optoelectronics. Molecular doping has emerged as a promising route to harness charge carrier density via charge transfer without compromising the structural integrity of perovskite. Nevertheless, the details on the underlying host-dopant interactions governing such process remain elusive. In this talk, we will report on the doping mechanism of p-type methylammonium tin-lead iodide films by employing 4-(1,3-Dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)phenyl)-N,N-dimethylbenzenamine (n-DMBI-H) as an n-type molecular dopant^[2]. Via a powerful combination of ab initio simulation and experimental techniques, we will describe the preferential dative bonding between amino groups in n-DMBI-H and surface Sn in perovskites as a key host-dopant interaction that facilitates electron transfer. To conclude, we will discuss the introduction of n-DMBI-H in p-i-n perovskite solar cells, which leads to fewer recombination losses and enhanced selectivity at perovskite/transport layer contacts. Our work provides a comprehensive picture of perovskite molecular doping that will have important implications for the design of perovskite optoelectronic applications.

References

- [1] Euvrard, J., Yan, Y. and Mitzi, D.B, *Nature Reviews Materials*, 2000, 6(6)
- [2] Scaccabarozzi, A.D., Basu, A., Anié, F., Liu, J., Zapata-Arteaga, O., Warren, R., Firdaus, Y., Nugraha, M.I., Lin, Y., Campoy-Quiles, M. and Koch, N. *Chemical Reviews*, 2021, 122(4).

Relativistic and QED corrections to one-bond indirect nuclear spin-spin couplings in X_2^{2+} and X_3^{2+} ions ($X = \text{Zn}, \text{Cd}, \text{Hg}$)

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The indirect spin-spin coupling tensor, \mathbf{J} , between mercury nuclei in Hg-containing systems can be of the order of few kHz and one of the largest measured. We analysed the physics behind the electronic mechanisms that contribute to the one- and two-bond couplings ${}^n\mathbf{J}_{\text{Hg-Hg}}$ ($n=1, 2$). We performed calculations for J -couplings in the ionized X_2^{2+} and X_3^{2+} linear molecules ($X = \text{Zn}, \text{Cd}, \text{Hg}$), within polarization propagator theory, using the random phase approximation and the pure zeroth-order approximation, with Dirac-Hartree-Fock and Dirac-Kohn-Sham orbitals, both at four-component and ZORA levels. We show that the “paramagnetic-like” mechanism contribute with more than 99.98% to the total isotropic component of the coupling tensor. By analyzing the molecular and atomic orbitals involved in the total value of the response function, we find that the s -type valence atomic orbitals have a predominant role in the description of the coupling. This fact allows us to develop an effective model from which QED effects on J -coupling in the aforementioned ions can be estimated. Those effects were found to be within the interval (0.7; 1.7)% of the total relativistic effect on isotropic one-bond ${}^1\mathbf{J}$ coupling, though ranging those corrections between the interval (-0.4; -0.2)% in Zn-containing ions, to (-1.2; -0.8)% in Hg-containing ions, to the total isotropic coupling constant in the studied systems. The estimated QED corrections show a dependence on the nuclear charge Z of each atom X in the form of a power-law $\propto Z^5$.

References

- [1] K. Koziol, I. A. Aucar and G. A. Aucar, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2019), 150(18), 184301.
- [2] Pyykkö, P., Zhao, L. B. *Journal of Physics B: Atomic, Molecular and Optical Physics* (2003), 36(8), 1469.
- [3] Gillespie, R. J., Granger, P., Morgan, K. R., & Schrobilgen, G. J. *Inorganic Chemistry* (1984), 23(7), 887-891.
- [4] Malleier, R., Kopacka, H., Schuh, W., Wurst, K., Peringer, P. *Chemical Communications* (2001), (1), 51-52.
- [5] Autschbach, J., Igna, C. D., Ziegler, T. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* (2003), 125(16), 4937-4942.
- [6] Autschbach, J., Sterzel, M. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* (2007), 129(36), 11093-11099.
- [7] DIRAC, Release DIRAC22 (2022), H. J. Aa. Jensen, R. Bast, A. S. P. Gomes, T. Saue, L. Visscher, et al.

The validity of the electric dipole approximation in x-ray spectroscopy

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In the UV-Vis regime, the wavelength of electromagnetic radiation is typically much larger than the spatial extent of the molecular system under consideration. Because of this, the electromagnetic wave can be approximated as a uniform electric field, which is referred to as the electric dipole approximation. In the x-ray regime, however, the wavelength of light and the molecular system can be of comparable size, implying the need to include effects beyond the electric dipole approximation in the simulation of x-ray spectroscopy. Additionally, the high energies involved in the experiment probe electrons that are buried deep inside the core. Especially for heavy nuclei, these electrons are most susceptible to relativistic effects. Therefore, proper simulations of x-ray spectroscopy should include relativity and multipolar effects.

Figure 1: Interaction of a molecule with linearly polarized light.

In our previous work, we have presented two methods to calculate molecular absorption intensities beyond the electric dipole approximation.[1,2] The first method, is based on the full-light matter interaction, implying that the interaction operator retains the same sinusoidal form as the electromagnetic fields from which it is derived. On the other hand, the second method, is based on an expansion of the absorption cross-section with respect to the wave vector, which ought to be truncated at some finite order in any practical application. Both of these schemes are based on a 4-component methodology, hence including the effects of relativity.[1] The aim of this talk is to present the implementation of these two methods and their application in x-ray absorption spectroscopy.

References

[1] van Horn, M.; Saue, T.; List, N. H. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* (2022), 156, 054113.

[2] List, N. H.; Melin, T. R. L.; van Horn, M.; Saue, T. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* (2020), 152, 184110.

Compared non-relativistic effects and relativistic effects on M_2 (M=;Nh, Fl, Mc, Lv, Ts, and Og)

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The title compounds are used to investigate the relativity in superheavy elements dimers from 7th row in the periodic table. The present purely theoretical molecular data suggest the domination of p-orbitals for chemical bonding with scalar relativistic effects and spin-orbit (SO) relativistic effects on superheavy elements.

In this study, the mainly two-component relativistic methods were applied to these molecules compared to four-component results. In particular, the molecular point group irreps can be illustrated instead of the jj -coupling states when Clebsch-Gordan coefficients is applied to the spin part at SO. Also, the relationship between jj -coupling states and π and σ bonding is presented using these homonuclear molecules.

Figure 1. The six molecular orbitals of Mc_2 .

References

- [1] P. Pyykkö, *Chemical Reviews*, (1988) **88**, 563–594.
- [2] P. Pyykkö and J. P. Desclaux, *Accounts of Chemical Research*, (1979) **12**, 276–281.
- [3] K. S. Pitzer, *Accounts of Chemical Research*, (1979) **12**, 271–276.
- [4] P. Christiansen, *Chemical physics letters*, (1984) **109**, 145–149.
- [5] V. Pershina, A. Borschevsky, J. Anton and T. Jacob, *The Journal of chemical physics* (2010) **132**, 194314.
- [6] K. Balasubramanian, *Relativistic effects in chemistry: part B: applications*. Wiley. (1997).

Variational Dirac–Coulomb approach with explicitly correlated basis functions

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The no-pair Dirac–Coulomb(–Breit) equation is solved using explicitly correlated Gaussian functions [1, 2, 3]. The explicitly correlated basis set significantly improves the description of the electron correlation compared to e.g. determinant basis set, however, the positive-energy projection is more complicated due to the lack of the underlying one-electron picture. Therefore, several positive-energy projectors are examined to achieve and justify the parts-per-billion convergence of the energy providing a starting point for further comparison and developments in relation with high-resolution atomic and molecular spectroscopy. The no-pair Dirac–Coulomb energy is compared with perturbative results for atomic and molecular systems with small nuclear charge numbers and it reproduces the perturbative expressions [4] up to $\alpha^3 E_h$ order.

Figure 1: The dependence of the Dirac–Coulomb no-pair energy, $(E_{\text{DC}}^{\text{proj}} - E_{\text{DC}}^{(2)}) / \langle \delta(\mathbf{r}_{12}) \rangle_{\text{nr}}$ on the fine-structure constant (α). The non-relativistic energy and the α^2 perturbative energy correction ($E_{\text{DC}}^{(2)}$) are extracted to highlight the agreement with the $\alpha^3 E_h$ perturbative corrections, $\varepsilon_{\text{CC}}^{++} \approx -3.24 \langle \delta(\mathbf{r}_{12}) \rangle_{\text{nr}} \alpha^3 E_h$ [4].

References

- [1] P. Jeszenszki, D. Ferenc, and E. Mátyus, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2021), 154, 224110. [arXiv](#)
- [2] P. Jeszenszki, D. Ferenc, and E. Mátyus, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2022), 156, 084111. [arXiv](#)
- [3] D. Ferenc, P. Jeszenszki, and E. Mátyus, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2022), 156, 084110. [arXiv](#)
- [4] J. Sucher, *Ph. D. Thesis* (1958), Columbia University.

Developing theoretical beamlines for ultrafast spectroscopy

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One of the most widely used way to understand a molecular system is to study its response to electromagnetic fields. Massive investments have been made, during the last two decades, in the advancement of experimental installations for the detection of increasingly sophisticated light-matter interaction, as exemplified by last generation synchrotron and (x-ray) free electron laser facilities. New ways of probing molecules and materials are emerging, addressing a broad range of scientific problems of both fundamental and applied character. For instance, developments in the field of ultrashort laser pulses have enabled the generation of broadband few- to sub-femtosecond pulses in the near-infrared to ultraviolet spectral regimes. These pulses paves way for exploring pure valence electron dynamics, without contributions from nuclear dynamics. In this, an attosecond pulse coherently populates dipole allowed electronic states, thereby creating an electronic wavepacket, which gives rise to a dynamical evolution of the system under study. These advances have prompted a need to formulate reliable theoretical and computational methodologies, as an essential component to interpret the experimental results and to design future experiments.

We present an extension of relativistic real-time time-dependent density functional theory to simulate attosecond transient absorption spectroscopy [1,2]. It is for valence-pump, followed by core-probe pulses with varying delays between them. This process captures the signature of the transient dynamics triggered by the pump pulse, imprinted onto the spectroscopic properties of the probe pulse. The implementation is performed in the relativistic DFT program ReSpect [3]. Some examples will be presented showcasing the applicability of the theoretical tool for simple molecular systems [4].

References

- [1] M. Repisky, L. Konecny, M. Kadek, S. Komorovsky, O. L. Malkin, Vladimir G. Malkin and K. Ruud, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* (2015), 11, 980.
- [2] M. Kadek, L. Konecny, B. Gao, M. Repisky and K. Ruud, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, (2015), 17, 22566.
- [3] M. Repisky, S. Komorovsky, M. Kadek, L. Konecny, U. Ekstrom, E. Malkin, M. Kaupp, K. Ruud, O. L. Malkina and V. G. Malkin, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2020), 152, 184101.
- [4] T. Moitra, L. Konecny, M. Kadek, M. Repisky, *In preparation* (2022).

High accuracy calculations of electron affinity of heavy and superheavy elements

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The electron affinities of heavy and superheavy elements (At, Ac, Lr, Nh, and Og) were calculated within the relativistic coupled cluster (CCSD(T)) approach. Major part of this research was carried out in collaboration with experimental groups, where we provide theoretical support for the challenging measurements on these atoms.

To obtain an estimate of the accuracy our predictions, we investigated various computational parameters (number of correlated electrons, choice of the Hamiltonian, basis set, etc.), and performed calculations for the lighter homologues. Our final values are obtained using the 4-component Dirac Hamiltonian, all electrons are correlated, and the results are extrapolated to the complete basis set limit and corrected for the Breit and QED contributions. We compared the results to other theoretical investigations and different sources of error are discussed in order to estimate the uncertainty of the predicted EA.

PROGRAM

REHE 2022

DAY 3

SEPTEMBER 28

EXTENDED LECTURE SESSION 03

From 08:45 to 09:30

INVITED TALKS SESSION 06

From 09:30 to 10:30

INVITED TALKS SESSION 07

From 11:00 to 12:30

INVITED TALKS SESSION 08

From 13:30 to 15:00

TRIP TO ASSISI

From 15:00 to 19:30

COFFEE BREAKS

From 10:30 to 11:00

LUNCH

From 12:30 to 13:30

DINNER

From 19:30 to 21:00

POSTER SESSION - Even numbers

From 21:00 to 23:00

EXTENDED LECTURE

ABSTRACT

DAY 3
SEPTEMBER 28

STEPHEN T. LIDDLE

"Actinide-Ligand Multiple Bonding: Marrying Experiment and Theory to Quantify Covalency"

Actinide-Ligand Multiple Bonding: Marrying Experiment and Theory to Quantify Covalency

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Over the past fifteen years the Liddle group has contributed to the development of the synthesis, reactivity, spectroscopy, magnetism, and quantum chemical characterisation of early actinide (uranium and thorium) -ligand multiple bonding [1-10]. Our motivation for undertaking this endeavour is simple – by marrying experimental and computational methodologies we wish to move from a qualitative regime to address a central aim of actinide science to quantify, and hence fully understand, the extent and nature of covalency in the chemical bonding of actinide ions. The study of early actinide systems is also an attractive area to research because the resulting body of work becomes the baseline from which to develop comparisons to transuranium [11] and lanthanide [12] analogues; this will in turn develop a well-rounded understanding of the f-elements more generally and help to contextualise their bonding with respect to the much more extensively investigated transition metals.

Here, we will provide an update on our research to date, including the evolution of our work to include transuranium derivatives. These complexes are now enabling quantification of actinide bonding and also actinide-actinide and actinide-lanthanide comparisons to be made.

We thank the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council, European Research Council, Royal Society, ActUsLab, Euroatom ENEN+, Cost Association, The University of Manchester, European Union Joint Research Centre Karlsruhe, Los Alamos National Laboratory, and the National Nuclear Laboratory for generous funding and support of our work.

References

- [1] Du J. *et al.*, *Nat. Commun.* (2021), 12, 5649.
- [2] Chatelain, L. *et al.*, *Nat. Commun.* (2020), 11, 337.
- [3] Du J. *et al.*, *Nat. Commun.* (2019), 10, 4203.
- [4] Wooles, A. J. *et al.*, *Nat. Commun.* (2018), 9, 2097.
- [5] Wildman, E. P. *et al.*, *Nat. Commun.* (2017), 8, 14769.
- [6] King, D. M. *et al.*, *Nat. Commun.* (2016), 7, 13773.
- [7] Gardner, B. M. *et al.*, *Nat. Chem.* (2015), 7, 582.
- [8] Cleaves, P. A. *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* (2014), 53, 10412.
- [9] King, D. M. *et al.*, *Nat. Chem.* (2013), 5, 482.
- [10] King, D. M. *et al.*, *Science*, (2012), 337, 717.
- [11] Dutkiewicz M. S. *et al.*, *Nat. Chem.* (2022), 14, 342.
- [12] Goodwin, C. A. P. *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* (2022), 144, 9764.

INVITED TALKS

ABSTRACT

DAY 3

SEPTEMBER 28

TONYA VITOVA

"Bonding interactions of the actinide elements probed by high resolution X-ray spectroscopy"

MAURO PERFETTI

"Magnetic anisotropy of heavy-elements molecular compounds: study and control"

PAOLA BELANZONI

"Intriguing features of the halogen bond revealed by spin-orbit coupling"

MINORI ABE

"Theoretical calculation of isotope fractionation in biotic uranium reduction"

INVITED TALKS

ABSTRACT

DAY 3

SEPTEMBER 28

JOEL CREUTZBERG

"Investigating relativistic effects for light-activated diazido Platinum complexes in aqueous environments"

DANIELE CESARINI

"The Leonardo Supercomputer at the Bologna Big Data Technopole and the CINECA's Evolution Roadmap"

IVANO TAVERNELLI

"Quantum computing applications in quantum chemistry"

LUCAS VISSCHER

"Electron correlation challenges in relativistic quantum chemistry"

Bonding interactions of the actinide elements probed by high resolution X-rayspectroscopy

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Understanding the electronic structure and chemical bonding properties of the actinide (An) elements poses a great challenge and frontier in fundamental chemistry and physics.¹ The An_{4,5} absorption edge core-to-core and valence band resonant inelastic X-ray scattering (CC/VB-RIXS) and high energy resolution X-ray absorption near edge structure (HR-XANES) techniques probe the occupied and unoccupied parts of the valence band of the actinide elements with extraordinary energy resolution and thus unique information on the chemical bond can be obtained.¹ A deep insight into the An electronic structures is for example essential to understand actinide environmental behaviour. All An M_{4,5} edge RIXS and HR-XANES studies are performed at the ACT station of the CAT-ACT beamline at the KIT Light Source.²

Spectroscopic and computational tools for probing in detail the An-ligand (U, Np, Pu or Am) bond covalency will be discussed.^{1,3,4} It will be shown that An 3d4f CC-RIXS can be used to measure spin-orbit coupling effects and is a probe of the localised and delocalised f electron density on the An atom. It will be demonstrated that the energy positions of the resonant peaks in the CC-RIXS/HR-XANES spectra strongly depend on the electron-electron/hole interactions in the intermediate and final state of the excitation process and thus these two effects are of importance for close agreement of calculated and experimental spectra.

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References

1. Vitova, T.; Pidchenko, I.; Fellhauer, D.; Bagus, P. S.; Joly, Y.; Pruessmann, T.; Bahl, S.; González-Robles, E.; Rothe, J.; Altmaier, M.; Denecke, M. A.; Geckeis, H., The role of the 5f valence orbitals of early actinides in chemical bonding. *Nature Communications* **2017**, *8*, 16053.
2. Schacherl, B.; Prussmann, T.; Dardenne, K.; Hardock, K.; Krepper, V.; Rothe, J.; Vitova, T.; Geckeis, H., Implementation of cryogenic tender X-ray HR-XANES spectroscopy at the ACT station of the CAT-ACT beamline at the KIT Light Source. *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation* **2022**, *29* (1), 80-88.
3. Bagus, P. S.; Schacherl, B.; Vitova, T., Computational and Spectroscopic Tools for the Detection of Bond Covalency in Pu(IV) Materials. *Inorganic Chemistry* **2021**, *60* (21), 16090-16102.
4. Vitova, T.; Pidchenko, I.; Schild, D.; Prüßmann, T.; Montoya, V.; Fellhauer, D.; Gaona, X.; Bohnert, E.; Rothe, J.; Baker, R. J.; Geckeis, H., Competitive Reaction of Neptunium(V) and Uranium(VI) in Potassium–Sodium Carbonate-Rich Aqueous Media: Speciation Study with a Focus on High-Resolution X-ray Spectroscopy. *Inorganic Chemistry* **2020**, *59* (1), 8-22.

Magnetic anisotropy of heavy-elements molecular compounds: study and control

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Magnetic anisotropy, i.e., the different magnetic response of a material depending on its orientation, is an important property in the field of quantum information [1]. Achieving a deep understanding and, ultimately, a full control over magnetic anisotropy is the key to design performant molecular magnetic materials such as Single Molecule Magnets, Magnetocaloric agents or Quantum Qubits. In this talk, an overview of how magnetic anisotropy of heavy elements complexes can be studied and exploited using torque magnetometry will be presented. Figure 1 shows three findings that will be highlighted: a) the f^{n+7} effect, i.e., the correspondence of magnetic reference frames between isostructural complexes differing by 7 4f-electrons [2], b) the use of external parameters such a temperature and magnetic field to manipulate the magnetic anisotropy [3,4] and c) how to probe molecular order on surface by exploiting magnetic anisotropy [5].

Figure 1. a) The f^{n+7} effect [2]. b) Magnetic anisotropy switch on a lanthanide complex [3,4] c) Molecular order on surface probed by torque magnetometry [5].

References

- [1] S. T. Liddle and J. van Slageren, *Chemical Society Reviews* (2015), 44, 6655.
- [2] M. Briganti, E. Lucaccini, L. Chelazzi, S. Ciattini, [...] and M. Perfetti, *Journal of the American Chemical Society* (2021), 143, 8108.
- [3] M. Perfetti, M. A. Sørensen, U. B. Hansen, H. Bamberger, [...] and J. Bendix, *Advanced Functional Materials* (2018), 28, 1801846.
- [4] M. Perfetti and J. Bendix, *Chemical Communications* (2018), 54, 12163.
- [5] M. Perfetti, M. Serri, L. Poggini, M. Mannini, [...] and R. Sessoli, *Advanced Materials* (2016), 28, 6946.

Intriguing features of the halogen bond revealed by spin-orbit coupling

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The effect of spin-orbit coupling (SOC) on the halogen bond involving astatine has been investigated using state-of-the-art two- and four-component relativistic calculations [1,2]. Adducts between Cl-X (X = Cl, Br, I and At) and ammonia, the Lewis base, have been selected to establish a trend along the halogen group. The SOC influence has been explored not only on the geometric and energetic features that can be used to characterize the halogen bond strength but also on the three main contributions to it that are the charge transfer, the “ σ -hole” (i.e. the localized region with a net positive electrostatic potential at the halogen site) and the “polar flattening” (which is related to the effective shape of the halogen site) [3]. A surprisingly large increase of the Cl-At dipole moment, due to the inclusion of SOC, has been worked out using four-component CCSD(T) reference calculations, indicating that this bond is significantly more ionic than one may predict. Due to the SOC effect, which induces a peculiar charge accumulation on the At side in the Cl-At dimer, a weakening of the astatine-mediated halogen bond occurs arising from the (i) reduced amount of charge transfer, (ii) decrease of the polar flattening and (iii) lowering of the short-range Coulomb potential (Figure 1). The electronic structure analysis of the Cl-At moiety allows for a rationalization of the SOC effects on all the considered features of the halogen bond, including an unprecedented unsymmetrical charge back-donation from Cl-At to ammonia.

Figure 1 Effect of SOC on the halogen bond involving astatine.

References

- [1] G. R. Desiraju et al., *Pure Appl. Chem.* (2013), 85, 1711-1713.
- [2] E. Rossi et al., *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* (2020), 22, 1897-1910.
- [3] G. Cavallo et al., *Chem. Rev.* (2016), 116, 2478-2601.

Theoretical calculation of isotope fractionation in biotic uranium reduction

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Some bacteria can reduce water-soluble uranium (VI) to water-insoluble uranium (IV). During this reduction, heavier isotope (²³⁸U) more reduces to U(IV) than lighter isotope (²³⁵U) with bacteria, whereas the isotopic trend is not significant or opposite in general abiotic cases [1] unless the abiotic reaction was tuned to be very slow [2]. To elucidate the mechanism of uranium reduction and isotope fractionation by bacteria, we calculated the equilibrium isotope fractionation coefficient (ϵ) for each reaction step, proposed in [3] and shown in Figure 1. The leading cause of isotope fractionation in heavy elements is called a nuclear volume effect, which arises from the electronic energy difference of different size of nuclear charge radii of two isotopes [4]. To calculate nuclear volume effects, we performed highly accurate relativistic calculations based on the X2C Hamiltonian using the Gaussian finite nucleus model in DIRAC16 program. Obtained theoretical results qualitatively reproduce the experimental trend that the heavier isotope is enriched in U(IV). However, the actual experiments underwent in the non-equilibrium condition. Hence, we invoke a steady-state model for isotope fractionation [5], which can link the calculated ϵ for each reaction step and the experimental non-equilibrium ϵ , and discuss the reaction mechanism more specifically [6].

Figure 1. A reaction model of the biotic uranium reduction and calculated ϵ

References:

- [1] M. Stylo et al. Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA. 112, 5619, 2015.
- [2] S. T. Brown et al. Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA. 115, 8688–8693, 2018.
- [3] M. Sundararajan et al. J. Phys. Chem. A. 112, 4451, 2008.
- [4] J. Bigeleisen, J. Am. Chem. Soc., 118, 3676-3680, 1996.
- [5] C. E. Rees, Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta, 37, 1141-1162, 1973.
- [6] A. Sato et al., Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta, 307, 212-227, 2021.

Investigating relativistic effects for light-activated diazido Platinum complexes in aqueous environments

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Light-activated transition metal complexes have been investigated for application in chemotherapy. One type of these complexes is octahedral diazido Platinum complexes [1]. The complexes are biologically inactive in the dark, and the light activation can occur at the site of the tumor, thus reducing side effects significantly. The optimal wavelength for activation is in the window transparent for human tissue, and it is therefore of interest to understand at which wavelengths this activation occurs. Previous studies have investigated this [2], but usually with TD-DFT without explicit inclusion of spin-orbit coupling. The few exceptions are two very recent studies [3,4] of which one is from our group [3].

Another important point is that the reaction takes place in the body, where it can be expected that the complexes are solvated, i.e., the solvation environment needs to be taken into consideration. For this purpose, we have enabled the use of the complex polarization propagator together with polarizable embedding (PE) and a two or four-component wavefunction [5]. The PE method explicitly includes large, complex environments, including both solvents and bio-molecules through point multipoles and polarizabilities. In this talk, I will describe how we have developed this method and how we have applied it for spectroscopic characterization of one of the platinum complexes with potential use in chemotherapy. I will show how both relativistic effects and the environment play a role in calculating spectra and suggest how this might influence the future design of complexes used in chemotherapy.

- [1] M. Imran, W. Ayub, I. S. Butler, and Z.-u. Rehman, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* (2018), 376, 405.
- [2] A. Y. Sokolov and H. F. Schaefer III, *Dalton Trans.* (2011), 40, 7571.
- [3] J. Creutzberg, E. D. Hedegård, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* (2020), 22, 27013.
- [4] L. Freitag, L. Gonzáles, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* (2021), 12, 4876
- [5] J. Creutzberg, E. D. Hedegård, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* (2022), accepted.

The Leonardo Supercomputer at the Bologna Big Data Technopole and the CINECA's Evolution Roadmap

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CINECA will host one of the three recent precursors of exascale systems. Leonardo supercomputing system will be installed on the newly built data center located in the Bologna Big Data Technopole. It will be capable of nearly 250 PFlops and equipped with over 100 petabytes of storage capacity, it will be based on Atos BullSequana XH2000 technology with over 13,000 GPUs based on NVIDIA Ampere architecture and NVIDIA Mellanox HDR InfiniBand. The system will provide over ten times the computing power of the current CINECA flagship system Marconi-100.

The Bologna Big Data Technopole would also include the hosting of INFN main data centre, the Tier-1 of CNAF in Bologna. Emilia Romagna Region and the ministry of university and research had already established a collaboration in order to promote the Technopole project to a national and international level. This collaboration was successful in obtaining the decision from the Council of the international intergovernmental body ECMWF to relocate its own data centre to Bologna Technopole. Therefore, by virtue of hosting ECMWF, CINECA, and INFN data centre, Bologna Technopole raises to become one of the main European hubs for computing and data processing.

In this talk, it will be presented the Leonardo Supercomputer covering all the technical aspects of the design of the supercomputing system architecture. Moreover, it will be presented the data centre of CINECA/INFN focusing on mechanical and electrical infrastructure specifically designed to support pre- and exascale systems. In conclusion, it will be presented the CINECA's evolution technology roadmap that, in the near future, will support Italian and European research communities with new generations of computing technology.

Quantum computing applications in quantum chemistry

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The original idea that a quantum *machine* can potentially solve many-body quantum mechanical problems more efficiently than classical computers is due to R. Feynman who proposed the use of quantum computers to investigate the fundamental properties of nature at the quantum scale. In particular, the solution of problems in electronic structure, many-body physics, and high energy physics (just to mention a few) is a challenging computational task for classical computers as the number of needed resources increases exponentially with the number of degrees of freedom. Thanks to the recent development of quantum technologies, we have now the possibility to address these classes of problems with the help of quantum computers. To achieve this goal, a number of quantum algorithms able to best exploit the potential quantum speedup of noisy state-of-the-art quantum computers as well as of the next generation of fault-tolerant quantum machines have been proposed [1,2].

In this talk, I will discuss applications of quantum computing in many-body physics and quantum chemistry, focusing on those aspects that are relevant to achieve quantum advantage in the medium and long run. In particular, I will present recent developments and results for electronic structure calculations [3], including the evaluation of ground and excited states properties [4], the calculation of nuclear forces for molecular dynamics [5], and the simulation of wavepacket dynamics [6-8].

- [1] N. Moll, et al., ‘Quantum optimization using variational algorithms on near-term quantum devices’, *Quantum Sci. Technol.*, **3**, 030503 (2018).
- [2] A. Kandala et al., ‘Hardware-efficient variational quantum eigensolver for small molecules and quantum magnets’, *Nature*, **549**, 242 (2017).
- [3] P. Baroutsos, et al., ‘Quantum algorithms for electronic structure calculations: Particle-hole Hamiltonian and optimized wave-function expansions’, *Phys. Rev. A*, **98**, 022322 (2018).
- [4] P. Ollitrault et al., ‘Quantum equation of motion for computing molecular excitation energies on a noisy quantum processor’, *Phys. Rev. Res.*, **2**, 043140 (2020).
- [5] O Sokolov, et al., ‘Microcanonical and finite-temperature ab initio molecular dynamics simulations on quantum computers’, *Phys. Rev. Res.*, **1**, 013125 (2021).
- [6] P.J. Ollitrault, et al., ‘Nonadiabatic molecular quantum dynamics with quantum computers’, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, **125**, 260511 (2020).
- [7] P.J. Ollitrault, et al., ‘Molecular Quantum Dynamics: A Quantum Computing Perspective’, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, **54**, 4229 (2021).
- [8] P.J. Ollitrault, et al., ‘Quantum algorithms for grid-based variational time evolution’, arXiv:2203.02521 (2022).

Electron correlation challenges in relativistic quantum chemistry

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In this presentation I will report on our progress on developing algorithms for relativistic quantum chemistry which go beyond the mean field approximation. I will first illustrate the challenges that may arise already in relatively small heavy element systems[1]. I will then consider a number of different approaches[2, 3, 4, 5] that each have their strong and weak points in tackling such challenges, focusing in particular on the emerging prospects[6, 7] of using quantum computers to describe the strongly correlated systems that are often encountered in heavy element chemistry.

References

- [1] J. V. Pototschnig, K. G. Dyall, A. S. P. Gomes, L. Visscher, *PCCP* **23** (2020) 22330-22343.
- [2] J. V. Pototschnig, A. Papadopoulos, D. I. Lyakh, M. Repisky, L. Halbert, A. S. P. Gomes, H. J. Å. Jensen, L. Visscher, *J. Chem. Theor. Comp.* **17** (2021) 5509-5529.
- [3] A. Förster, L. Visscher, *Frontiers in Chemistry* **9** (2021) 36591.
- [4] S. Yalouz, B. Senjean, J. Gunther, F. Buda, T. E. O'Brien, L. Visscher, *Quantum Science and Technology* **6** (2021) 024004.
- [5] M. Rodríguez-Mayorga, K. J.H. Giesbertz, L. Visscher, *SciPost Chem.* **1** (2022) 004.
- [6] L. Veis *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. A.* **85** (2012) 030304.
- [7] T. E. OBrien *et al.*, *Npj Quantum Information* **5** (2019) 113.

POSTER SESSION EVEN NUMBERS

ABSTRACT

DAY 3

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"Multiwavelet implementation of the Dirac Equation"

DIEGO SORBELLI

"On the nature of the aurophilic interaction: a quest for covalent and spin-orbit coupling contributions"

IGNACIO AGUSTÍN AUCAR

"Parity-violating nuclear spin-rotation tensors in tetrahedral molecules"

JINXIA HU

"The total atomic energies of the ground state configurations of many-electron isoelectronic series"

JUAN JOSÉ AUCAR

"Relativistic corrections to the electric field gradient given by linear response elimination of the small component (LRESC) formalism"

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"Calculation of Vibrational Frequencies with Four-Component Relativistic DFT Method"

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"Computational Modelling of Electrocatalytic Processes on Coordination Polymers"

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DAY 3

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"Relativistic Fock-space coupled cluster calculations for extracting nuclear moments and charge radii from spectroscopy"

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"Relativistic electronic structure calculations for measurements of symmetry violations: A matter of precision"

Multiwavelet implementation of the Dirac Equation

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We present our prototype implementation of the four-component Dirac equation within the Hartree-Fock formalism.

The current implementation features the full two-electron interaction including Gaunt and Gauge terms. We show that the Multiwavelet (MW) formalism greatly simplifies the implementation thanks to a code semantic which closely resembles the theoretical formulation.

The implementation makes use of the MRCPP library to handle the mathematical operations with MWs, and the Python interface VAMPyR which enables very fast prototyping.

On the nature of the aurophilic interaction: a quest for covalent and spin-orbit coupling contributions

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The term “aurophilicity” describes the unexpected attraction between two or more gold centres in compounds where the metals are already chemically saturated according to conventional valence concepts: in its most simplistic form, the message reads: ‘gold is drawn to gold’ [1]. Despite this effect may lead to the formation of a wide variety of supramolecular structures with peculiar properties and to possible applications as optically active materials and homogeneous catalysts [2], the nature of the aurophilic interaction remains still poorly understood.

In this contribution, we elucidate the nature of the Au-Au interaction for the simple model dimer [ClAuPH₃]₂ using state-of-the-art computational techniques. Several well-established tools for the analysis of chemical bonding based on Density Functional Theory (*i.e.*, Energy Decomposition Analysis [3], Natural Orbitals for Chemical Valence [4] and Charge Displacement [5] approaches) as well as accurate domain-based local pair natural orbital coupled cluster DLPNO-CCSD(T) [6] (*i.e.*, Local Energy Decomposition [7]) are employed for a thorough analysis of the Au-Au interaction in the dimer. Special emphasis is on understanding the weight of any possible covalent contribution to the gold-gold weak bonding. Furthermore, a quantitative assessment of the impact of spin-orbit coupling on the strength of the interaction is carried out.

References

- [1] H. Schmidbaur, *Gold Bulletin* (2000), 33, 3.
- [2] N. Mirzadeh, S. H. Privér, A. J. Blake, H. Schmidbaur and S. K. Bhargava, *Chem. Rev.* (2020), 120, 7551.
- [3] L. Zhao, M. von Hopffgarten, D. M. Andrada and G. Frenking, *WIREs Comput. Mol. Sci.* (2018), 8, e1345.
- [4] M. Mitoraj and A. Michalak, *J. Mol. Model.* (2007), 13, 347.
- [5] G. Bistoni, S. Rampino, F. Tarantelli and L. Belpassi, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2015), 142, 084112.
- [6] F. Neese, A. Hansen and D. G. Liakos, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2009), 131, 064103.
- [7] W. B. Schneider, G. Bistoni, M. Sparta, M. Saitow, C. Riplinger, A. A. Auer and F. Neese, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* (2016), 12, 4778.

Parity-violating nuclear spin-rotation tensors in tetrahedral molecules

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We present a four-component relativistic study of nuclear spin-dependent parity-violation (PV) effects due to electroweak interactions in nuclear spin-rotation tensors [1]. The proposed theoretical formalism is based on the relativistic polarization propagator theory, employing a Dirac-Coulomb (DC) Hamiltonian. The calculations made using the DIRAC code [2] allow planning and interpreting possible future experiments aimed at

Calculated values of $|\Delta M_{X,iso}| = 2 |M_{X,iso}^{PV}|$ (in μHz) for the X nuclei in NXABC systems ($X = {}^{183}\text{W}, {}^{235}\text{U}$; $A, B, C = \text{H}, \text{F}, \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$) using the DC Hamiltonian at the DFT-PBE0 level of approach and dyall.cv3z basis set for all the elements.

giving a strict probe of the Standard Model of particle physics, based on the observation of parity-violation effects on spectroscopic molecular parameters. An exploratory application of this theory to a set of chiral molecules reveals the crucial importance of including relativistic effects to adequately describe these contributions. Four-component calculations of isotropic parity-violating nuclear spin-rotation constants allow estimation of frequency differences up to 0.14 mHz between the two enantiomers of the NUHFBr and NUHFI molecules. In addition, it is observed that in the molecular systems containing H and F the PV effects are

enhanced, as it also occurs for the parity-nonconservation effects in the NMR shieldings of NWXYZ ($X, Y, Z = \text{H}, \text{F}, \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$) molecules [3].

References

- [1] I. A. Aucar and A. Borschevsky, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2021), 155, 134307.
- [2] DIRAC, a relativistic ab initio electronic structure program, Release DIRAC22 (2022), written by H. J. Aa. Jensen, R. Bast, A. S. P. Gomes, T. Saue and L. Visscher, with contributions from I. A. Aucar, V. Bakken, C. Chibueze, J. Creutzberg, et al.
- [3] S. Nahrwold, R. Berger and P. Schwerdtfeger, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2014), 140, 024305.

The total atomic energies of the ground state configurations of many-electron isoelectronic series

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Accurate electronic binding energies are required in many fields of physics and physical chemistry. When moving to high- Z systems, relativistic effects bound-state quantum-electrodynamics corrections and become more important, and can change the level order in many elements. Results that have been used to provide the difference in binding energy between two arbitrary charge states were provided in [1,2]. In [1] non-relativistic approximations were used and in [2], the right ground state was not always properly identified when the ground configuration was very different from what was expected.

In the present work, we have performed an extensive systematic study of atomic binding energies covering many different outer-shell configurations and total angular momenta, using the Multi-Configurational Dirac–Fock method, for the isoelectronic series of elements between hydrogen and Dubnium (105 electrons). In each isoelectronic series we have considered all atomic numbers from neutral up to $Z=118$. Strong correlation effects could change the order however, in particular close to crossing point between two possible ground configurations. Improved self-energy corrections have been added [3,4]. These calculations also allow to evaluate outer electron binding energy by difference of the total binding energies of system with a difference of charge of one unit. Extension to Oganesson and atomic numbers up to 170 are in the way.

References

- [1] T. A. Carlson, J. C. W. Nestor, N. Wasserman, and J. D. McDowell, *Atomic Data and Nuclear Data Tables* **2**, 63 (1970).
- [2] G. C. Rodrigues, P. Indelicato, J. P. Santos, P. Patté, and F. Parente, *Atomic Data and Nuclear Data Tables* **86**, 117 (2004).
- [3] P. Indelicato, U. Jentschura, and P. J. Mohr, *in to be published* (2022).
- [4] P. Indelicato and P. J. Mohr, *in to be published* (2022).

Relativistic corrections to the electric field gradient given by linear response elimination of the small component (LRESC) formalism

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In this work we analyze relativistic effects on the electric field gradients (EFGs) via the linear response elimination of the small component scheme (LRESC) in order to give insight of the electronic origin of relativistic corrections. Originally developed for magnetic shielding constant, LRESC has been applied in many molecular properties and is applied to EFG. Within LRESC we obtain relativistic corrections to EFG in terms of $1/c$ (the speed of light) formally showing that, up to first order ($1/c^2$), there are no virtual pair contributions, recovering the so-called *no-pair* approximation. Virtual xpair contributions and triplet corrections arise at second order ($1/c^4$) [1]. Within the LRESC scheme it is possible to analyze the electronic mechanisms coming from the small and large components of the 4c wave function, so that we included all triplet corrections of $1/c^4$ order coming from both components.

To assess the LRESC description of EFGs, we applied it to a simple heavy atom containing set of benchmark molecular systems and compared with previous results [2, 3, 4], HX ($X = \text{F, Cl, Br, I, At}$), linear HgX_2 ($X = \text{Cl, Br, I}$) molecules and dihalogen molecules XY ($X, Y = \text{F, Cl, Br, I, At}$). Relativistic four-component calculations were performed and taken as reference.

LRESC shows a good performance, providing results close to four-component (4c) ones for molecules containing atoms belonging up to the fifth row of the Periodic Table. When heavier nuclei are involved the difference among LRESC and 4c values reaches up to 5%. The most important relativistic correction given by LRESC comes from *mass-velocity* related contribution (Δ^{Mv}) which represents close to 80% of the nonrelativistic result for At in HAt and At_2 molecules. For Hg in HgX_2 molecular systems, Δ^{Mv} is also the most important correction representing close to 60% of the nonrelativistic part. In HgX_2 molecules, LRESC corrections show a low variation when the weight of the halogen, X , increases. LRESC results are in very good agreement with previous ones for halogen halides, but it shows a need of inclusion of higher order contributions, beyond $1/c^2$, when applied to Hg in HgX_2 set and two heavy atom containin molecules.

LRESC can be applied at Hartree–Fock as well as Density Functional Theory levels, therefore we also analyze correlation effects on EFG showing that relativity enhances correlation effects and both effects are not additive [5].

References

- [1] J. I. Melo, A. F. Maldonado, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.* 2019, 119 (15), e25935.L.
- [2] Cheng, J. Gauss, *J. Chem. Phys.* 2011, 135, 084114.
- [3] M. Filatov, W. Zou, D. Cremer, *J. Chem. Phys.* 2012, 137, 054113.
- [4] V. Arcisauskaite, S. Knecht, S. P. A. Sauer, L. Hemmingsen, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 2012, 14, 2651.
- [5] J. J. Aucar, A. F. Maldonado, J. I. Melo, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.* 2021, 121 (20), e26769.

Calculation of Vibrational Frequencies with Four-Component Relativistic DFT Method

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Relativistic four-component method for calculating molecular hessian (thus also harmonic vibrational frequencies) is currently not implemented in any available computational chemistry program package. This means that there is no method to accurately calculate harmonic vibrational frequencies for systems that include heavy atoms. Therefore, the aim of this project was to develop such a method. Our approach is fully numerical, which means that the hessian is calculated as the second derivative of the energy using finite differences of the molecular energy with respect to geometrical distortions of the nuclei.

Next, in order to study the importance of relativistic effects on harmonic vibrational frequencies calculations have been performed for 15 hydrides (H₂X, X = O, S, Se, Te, Po; XH₃, X = N, P, As, Sb, Bi; and XH₄, X = C, Si, Ge, Sn, Pb) as well as for HC≡CPbH₃. The influences of the choice of basis set, exchange-correlation functional, and step length for the numerical differentiation on the calculated harmonic vibrational frequencies have also been tested, and the method has been found to be numerically robust. Relativistic effects are noticeable for the heavier congeners H₂Te and H₂Po, SbH₃ and BiH₃, and SnH₄ and PbH₄ and are much more pronounced for the vibrational modes with higher frequencies. Spin-orbit effects constitute a very small fraction of the total relativistic effects, except for H₂Te and H₂Po. For HC≡CPbH₃ we find that only the frequencies of the modes with large contributions from Pb displacements are significantly affected by relativity.

This project is considered a stepping stone towards the development of a four-component relativistic numerical method for calculating zero-point vibrational corrections to NMR parameters (spin–spin coupling constants and shielding constants).

Computational Modelling of Electrocatalytic Processes on Coordination Polymers

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One of the main pathways to produce molecular hydrogen is electrochemical water splitting. [1] To increase the efficiency of this process, the overpotential for the oxygen evolution reaction must be minimized. This can be achieved through the use of electrocatalysts. [2] Among the numerous families of catalysts studied and optimized over the years with this purpose, coordination polymers (CPs) recently gained great attention. [3] In this work, we initially defined an accurate computational protocol for the study of electrocatalytic processes on one-dimensional CPs containing first row transition metals (Ni, Co, Fe). The protocol was experimentally validated and then used to shed light into the origin of the catalytic activity of these systems towards water oxidation.

Figure 1. a) Water oxidation catalytic mechanism in acidic (yellow) and alkaline (blue) conditions. b) Reaction free energies for nickel (violet), cobalt (green) and iron (light blue) in the CPs.

References

- [1] Ursua, A., Gandia, L. M., Sanchis, P., *Proc. IEEE* (2012), 100 (2), 410–426.
- [2] Suen, N.-T., Hung, S.-F., Quan, Q., Zhang, N.; Xu, Y.-J., Chen, H. M., *Chem. Soc. Rev.* (2017), 46 (2), 337–365.
- [3] Batten, S. R., Champness, N. R., Chen, X.-M., Garcia-Martinez, J., Kitagawa, S., Öhrström, L., O’Keeffe, M., Paik Suh, M., Reedijk, J., *Pure Appl. Chem.* (2013), 85 (8), 1715–1724.

Topological Data Analysis in quantum chemistry – what can new data abstraction tell us about the role of relativistic effects on bonding and reactivity?

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We demonstrate the Topological Data Analysis (TDA) of selected molecular descriptors typically employed to study inter- and intra-molecular interactions and reactivity of molecular complexes with heavy atoms. The analysis of such descriptors, typically expressed as functions of the electron density, kinetic energy density, and electrostatic potential, to name but a few, in real space, can be very insightful. However, most visualization and data summarization methods that currently accompany quantum chemistry calculations are prone to errors and limitations, such as numerical bias, overcrowded representations, or the dependence on manually-tuned parameters. Consequently, complex chemical problems, such as an interplay of relativistic effects, electron correlation, and environment (e.g., solvent) presence, pose a challenge for analysis techniques. Here we introduce fundamental methods from applied topology to encode the chemical information into new data abstractions. In particular, we show how to detect and quantify topological features robustly and track their evolution across various time- and length scales. Our study contributes to the discussion of the future of Quantum Chemistry Topology (QCT) and proposes TDA as its modern complement.

Relativistic Fock-space coupled cluster calculations for extracting nuclear moments and charge radii from spectroscopy

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Atomic structure calculations in combination with spectroscopic measurements are very effective for extracting nuclear properties independent of nuclear models. Predicted mass- and field shift factors allow for determining the changes in nuclear charge radii from measured line shifts across isotopes, while hyperfine structure measurements combined with calculations of the electrons' magnetic field and electric field gradient give direct access to nuclear dipole and quadrupole moments [1,2]. We use the high-accuracy relativistic Fock-space coupled cluster method [3] with the finite field approach [4] to determine these isotope shift and hyperfine structure parameters. Basis set, electron correlation and relativistic effects are investigated to assign uncertainties on the calculated values. This is essential when combining our results with experimental data.

References

- [1] F. P. Gustafsson, C. M. Ricketts, M. L. Reitsma et al., *Phys. Rev. A* 102, 052812 (2020).
- [2] A. Kanellakopoulos, X. F. Yang, M. L. Bissell, M. L. Reitsma et al., *Phys. Rev. C* 102, 054331 (2020).
- [3] U. Kaldor and E. Eliav, *Adv. Quantum Chem.* 31, 313 (1998).
- [4] H.J. Monkhorst, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.*, 12: 421-432 (1977).

Environmental Effects with Frozen-Density Embedding in the Real-Time Time-Dependent Dirac-Kohn-Sham framework.

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Frozen Density Embedding (FDE)^[1,2] represents a versatile embedding scheme which allows to model complex molecular systems by partitioning the total system into sub-units: the environmental effects onto a given subsystem is described by accounting quantum mechanically for the surrounding subsystems through their electron density.

The accurate modeling of properties of matter when heavy elements are involved requires the inclusion of relativistic corrections. The Dirac-Kohn-Sham (DKS) method allows one to treat electron correlation and relativistic effects on the same footing.

The response of electrons in atoms and molecules to an applied external electro-magnetic field can be efficiently treated employing Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory (TDDFT) in the real-time domain (RT-TDDFT)^[3].

We extend the full 4-component relativistic RT-TDDKS^[4] method, as implemented in the BERTHA code, to include environmental and confinement effects with the FDE scheme (RT-TDDKS-in-DFT FDE)^[5].

Moreover, we demonstrate that the implementation of rather complex numerical algorithms can be enormously facilitated by BERTHA's python API (PyBERTHA) which, besides all the well-known Python advantages, eases the interoperability with other FDE implementations available through the PyADF framework.

References:

1. Wesolowski, T. A.; Warshel, A. Frozen density functional approach for ab initio calculations of solvated molecules. *J. Chem. Phys.* 1993, 97, 8050–8053.
2. Höfener, S.; Gomes, A. S. P.; Visscher, L. Molecular properties via a subsystem density functional theory formulation: a common framework for electronic embedding. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2012, 136(4), 044104.
3. Lopata, K.; Govind, N. Modeling Fast Electron Dynamics with Real-Time Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory: Application to Small Molecules and Chromophores. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 2011, 7, 1344–1355
4. De Santis, M.; Storchi, L.; Belpassi, L.; Quiney, H. M.; Tarantelli, F. PyBERTHART: A Relativistic Real-Time Four-Component TDDFT Implementation Using Prototyping Techniques Based on Python. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 2020, 16, 2410–2429.
5. De Santis, M.; Sorbelli, D.; Vallet, V.; Gomes, A. S. P.; Storchi, L.; Belpassi, L. Frozen-Density Embedding for including environmental effects in the Dirac-Kohn-Sham theory: an implementation based on density fitting and prototyping techniques. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2205.05523>

The Dirac equation in strong Coulomb fields

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Electrons bound by the external field of a nucleus are relativistically described by the Dirac equation and have a spectrum in the region $-mc^2 < E < mc^2$. For extremely heavy nuclei the bound state solution can become embedded in the negative continuum region. The eigenvalue of this supercritical state is complex and consequently the wavefunction shows resonance behaviour.

Although the solution can be continued into the complex domain, the orthogonality between the states is not necessarily guaranteed. This leads to several mathematical and interpretational difficulties. We present an analytical analysis of this fundamental problem and from a computational perspective, we discuss the challenges this creates in the implementation of numerical packages such as GRASP and MCDHF.

Calculations of the electron affinity of polonium at the CCSD(T) level

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The electron affinity (EA) is a fundamental atomic property which, together with the ionization potential (IP), allows to predict the physico-chemical behaviour of an element such as the electronegativity and the basicity, among others [1]. In the periodic table, polonium is one of the latest elements of the 6th row whose EA remains unknown. It will be measured in the near future at ISOLDE (CERN) by means of photodetachment spectroscopy, with an experimental set-up similar to the one recently used for measuring the EA of Astatine [2]. Herein, we aim to predict the value of the EA of polonium with state-of-the-art single reference CCSD(T) calculations in order to support the experiment and help in the interpretation of the resulting spectra. To do so, we provide a large exploration of the computational parameters (cardinality, augmentation, number of correlated electrons, etc.) to reach a meV accuracy within a reasonable computation cost. This approach, which allows to set an uncertainty on the prediction, is assessed by the calculation of the EA of tellurium, the lighter homologue of Po, where experimental data is available and allows for comparison. Finally, the results are compared to previous theoretical work, where various methods such as MCDHF, CASPT2 or RECP-ccaCA among others, were used to predict the value of the electron affinity of Po [3-7].

References

- [1] Leimbach, David, et al. "The electron affinity of astatine." *Nature communications* 11.1 (2020): 1-9.
- [2] Nichols, Miranda. *Preparation of negative ion beams for the determination of the electron affinity of polonium by laser photodetachment*. No. CERN-INTC-2021-011.2021.
- [3] Borschevsky, Anastasia, et al. "Ionization potentials and electron affinities of the superheavy elements 115–117 and their sixth-row homologues Bi, Po, and At." *Physical Review A* 91.2 (2015): 020501.
- [4] Laury, Marie L., and Angela K. Wilson. "Examining the heavy p-block with a pseudopotential-based composite method: Atomic and molecular applications of rp-ccCA." *The Journal of chemical physics* 137.21 (2012): 214111.
- [5] Zeng, Tao, Dmitri G. Fedorov, and Mariusz Klobukowski. "Multireference study of spin-orbit coupling in the hydrides of the 6p-block elements using the model core potential method." *The Journal of chemical physics* 132.7 (2010): 074102.
- [6] Roos, Björn O., et al. "Main group atoms and dimers studied with a new relativistic ANO basis set." *The Journal of Physical Chemistry A* 108.15 (2004): 2851-2858.
- [7] Li, Junqin, et al. "Theoretical study for the electron affinities of negative ions with the MCDHF method." *Journal of Physics B: Atomic, Molecular and Optical Physics* 45.16 (2012): 165004.

Assessing MP2 frozen natural orbitals for relativistic electronic structure

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The $O(N^6)$ computation cost is a bottleneck preventing performing Coupled-Cluster (CC) on large systems, particularly when employing 4-component based relativistic Hamiltonians, for which in practice one often uses uncontracted basis set generating large virtual molecular orbitals spaces.

The canonical Hartree-Fock (HF) orbitals are not the most compact representation for post HF method. On other hand, using natural orbital is an efficient way to reduce the orbital space and maintains most of the accuracy. We therefore implemented the MP2 frozen natural orbital (FNO) method [1] in the Exacorr code [2], with the particularity that our implementation can generate both complex and quaternion FNOs, and also express these in AO basis. It also allows us to obtain CCSD natural orbitals on AO basis, which can be subsequently used in analysis. We have investigated the orbital truncation errors in both correlation energy and molecular properties including dipole, quadrupole moment, electric field gradient, for hydrogen halides HX (X=F, Cl, Br, I, At, Ts), and parity violation for the H₂X₂ (X= O, S, Se, Te, Po) molecules. We find that FNO indeed accelerates rapidly the correlation energy convergence. For properties, truncated FNO spaces seem to slightly outperform canonical HF orbitals, and to provide reliable estimates for the molecular properties obtained for complete virtual spaces [3].

References

- [1] T. L. Barr, E. R. Davidson, *Phys. Rev. A* 1970, **1**, 644; A. G. Taube, R. J. Bartlett, *J. Chem. Phys.* 2008, **128**, 164101
- [2] J. V. Pototschnig, A. Papadopoulos, D. I. Lyakh, M. Repisky, L. Halbert, A. S. P. Gomes, H- JAa. Jensen, L. Visscher, *J. Chem. Theory. Comput.* 2021, **17**, 5509
- [3] X. Yuan, L. Visscher, ASP. Gomes, *J. Chem. phys.* 2022, **arXiv:2202.01146**

Relativistic electronic structure calculations for measurements of symmetry violations: A matter of precision

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High-precision experiments to measure parity (P), and parity and time-reversal (P, T) violation using paramagnetic molecules are a promising route to look for physics beyond the Standard Model of particle physics. Using close-lying opposite-parity molecular states enhances the symmetry-violating experimental signals. This enhancement is purely relativistic and increases with the atomic number [1], making systems containing heavy atoms ideal for symmetry-violation experiments. The enhancement factor can not be measured separately and therefore electronic structure theory is needed to determine its value. This work presents the molecular enhancement for the nuclear spin-dependent P-violating anapole moment in the diatomic molecules containing lanthanum and lutetium heavy atoms. We employ the finite field approach with the relativistic 4-components coupled-cluster method in the DIRAC program [2]. In addition, we include the enhancement factor for the P, T-violating electron electric dipole moment, the P, T-violating electron-nucleus interaction, and the P, T-violating nuclear magnetic quadrupole moment. We pursue a systematic study to estimate the effect of various computational parameters, such as the basis set and electron correlation, on the calculated properties. We have found a consistent dependence of the different symmetry-violating properties with the computational parameters leading to similar uncertainties in the calculated properties. The provided precision in our calculations is approximately 6% and makes the reported enhancement factors suitable for extracting the relevant fundamental properties from the experimental measurements.

References

- [1] Bouchiat M.A., Bouchiat C.C. *Journal de Physique* (1974), 35, 899-927.
- [2] Saue T, Bast R, Gomes AS, et al. *The Journal of chemical physics* (2020), 152, 204104.

PROGRAM

REHE 2022

DAY 4

SEPTEMBER 29

EXTENDED LECTURE SESSION 04

From 08:45 to 09:30

INVITED TALKS SESSION 09

From 09:30 to 10:30

INVITED TALKS SESSION 10

From 11:00 to 12:30

INVITED TALKS SESSION 11

From 14:30 to 16:30

COFFEE BREAKS

From 10:30 to 11:00

From 16:30 to 17:00

LUNCH

From 12:30 to 13:30

DISCUSSION NEXT REHE

From 18:30 to 19:30

SOCIAL DINNER

From 20:00 to 23:30

EXTENDED LECTURE

ABSTRACT

DAY 4
SEPTEMBER 29

CHRISTOPH H. KEITEL

"Extreme field calculations for Penning ion traps and EBITs and corresponding strong laser field scenarios"

Extreme field calculations for Penning ion traps and EBITs and corresponding strong laser field scenarios

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An overview is given on high-precision calculations for Penning ion trap experiments with focus on g factor, transition and binding energy evaluations and searches for new physics [1,2]. Corresponding calculations are presented for EBIT experiments [3] and new results on the muonic fine structure anomaly [4]. Finally, similar concepts are introduced for extreme field laser scenarios [5].

References

- [1] T. Sailer et al., arXiv:2204.12182, *Nature* in press (2022).
P. Filianin et al., *Physical Review Letters* (2021), Vol. 127, pp. 072502.
R. X. Schüssler et al., *Nature* (2020), Vol. 581, pp. 42-46.
- [2] V. Debierre, C. H. Keitel, and Z. Harman, *Physics Letters B* (2020), Vol. 807, pp. 135527.
V. Debierre, C. H. Keitel, and Z. Harman, arXiv:2202.01668 (2022).
- [3] S. Kühn et al., arXiv:2201.09070 (2022).
- [4] I. A. Valuev, G. Colò, X. Roca-Maza, C. H. Keitel, and N. S. Oreshkina, *Physical Review Letters* (2022), Vol. 128, pp. 203001.
- [5] Y.-F. Li, Y.-Y. Chen, K. Z. Hatsagortsyan, and C. H. Keitel, *Physical Review Letters* (2022), Vol. 128 (17), pp. 174801.

INVITED TALKS

ABSTRACT

DAY 4

SEPTEMBER 29

SANG-KIL SON

"Relativistic effects in x-ray multiphoton ionization dynamics"

MICHAL REPISKY

"Modern X-ray spectroscopies with atomic mean-field X2C Hamiltonians"

HARRY M. QUINEY

"Calculation of Breit and QED effects using Gaussian spinor basis functions"

KENNETH GEORGE DYALL

"Basis Sets for Relativistic Atomic and Molecular Calculations"

MAEN SALMAN

"Vacuum polarization in the finite basis problem"

ALESSANDRO ERBA

"Theoretical study of properties of radioactive molecules"

INVITED TALKS

ABSTRACT

DAY 4

SEPTEMBER 29

MARIUS KADEK

"Efficient all-electron four-component Kohn--Sham theory for relativistic band structures and properties of periodic solids"

VOLKER BLUM

"Relativistic Effects in Large, Complex Systems in an All-Electron Framework Based on Numeric Atom-Centered Basis Sets"

SILVIA PICOZZI

"Modelling of Spin-Orbit Coupling Effects in Ferroelectrics"

ANDRÉ SEVERO PEREIRA GOMES

"Relativistic correlated electronic structure and the calculation of accurate ground-state, core and valence properties of heavy element species"

LAN CHENG

"Analytic gradient techniques for spinor-based relativistic coupled-cluster theory"

XIAOSONG LI

"Four-Component Relativistic Multireference Methods: Find the Balance between Relativistic Effects and Electron Correlation"

Relativistic effects in x-ray multiphoton ionization dynamics

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X-ray Free-Electron Lasers (XFELs) have brought an impact on various scientific areas across physics, chemistry, materials science, and life science. When an atom or a molecule is exposed to an intense x-ray pulse that is generated by XFEL, it is ionized to a highly charged ion via a sequence of single-photon ionization and accompanying relaxation processes. Understanding of this *x-ray multiphoton ionization dynamics* is crucial for most XFEL applications. To this end, we have developed the dedicated toolkits to investigate x-ray-induced processes and to simulate ionization dynamics. If x-ray multiphoton ionization involves deep inner-shell electrons in heavy atoms, energy shifts by relativistic effects play an important role in ionization dynamics [1,2]. In this talk, we will present recent XFEL studies of atomic and molecular systems containing heavy atoms irradiated by intense XFEL pulses [1–5]. In particular, we will demonstrate how the relativistic effects are exhibited in x-ray multiphoton ionization dynamics of xenon atoms [1,2], in combination with resonances of highly charged ions that are initially hidden in neutral xenon atoms [1–3]. In molecular cases [4,5] we did not take relativistic effects into account, but this remains a challenge for the future.

Figure 1. Charge-state distributions of xenon after interacting with ultraintense x-ray pulses. Nonrelativistic and relativistic XATOM calculations are compared with experimental data.

References

- [1] K. Toyota, S.-K. Son, and R. Santra, *Phys. Rev. A* (2017), 95, 043412.
- [2] B. Rudek et al., *Nat. Commun.* (2018), 9, 4200.
- [3] S.-K. Son, R. Boll, and R. Santra, *Phys. Rev. Res.* (2020), 2, 023053.
- [4] X. Li et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* (2021), 127, 093202.
- [5] R. Boll et al., *Nat. Phys.* (2022), 18, 423–428.

Modern X-ray spectroscopies with atomic mean-field X2C Hamiltonians

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Recent years have seen a surge in the development of X-ray instrumentation in the form of fourth-generation synchrotron facilities, including X-ray free-electron lasers generating intense isolated soft X-ray pulses with sub-femtosecond temporal widths, as well as tabletop X-ray sources via high-harmonic generation. These advances drive the widespread adoption of X-ray spectroscopies and, in turn, prompt the development of computational methods capable of accurately and efficiently predicting and interpreting both standard and novel X-ray experiments.

From a computational point of view, X-ray spectroscopies are challenging, as they require a uniformly accurate description of both core and valence orbitals and accurate description of highly excited electronic states. The core orbitals will be significantly affected by relativistic effects, both through scalar relativistic effects as well as the spin-orbit splitting of degenerate p and d core orbitals, leading to $L_{2/3}$ and $M_{4/5}$ edges in X-ray spectra.

In this talk, we will present some of our recent theoretical advances towards efficient relativistic calculation of different X-ray spectroscopies based on an eXact two-component (X2C) Hamiltonian framework. Starting from self-consistent field (SCF) atomic mean-field (amf) quantities, we present two simple, yet computationally efficient and numerically accurate matrix-algebraic approaches to correct both scalar-relativistic *and* spin-orbit two-electron picture-change effects (PCE) arising within the X2C framework. Both approaches, dubbed *amfX2C* and *e(xtended)amfX2C*, allow us to uniquely tailor PCE corrections to mean-field models, *viz.* Hartree-Fock or Kohn-Sham DFT, in the latter case also avoiding the need of a point-wise calculation of exchange-correlation PCE corrections. We assess the numerical performance of these PCE correction models on X-ray absorptions near $L_{2,3}$ - and $M_{4,5}$ -edges in closed-shell transition metal and actinide compounds with different central atoms, ligands, and oxidation states. The variational inclusion of relativistic effects allows us to disentangle errors in conventional DFT studies due to self-interaction errors and the approximate treatment (or neglect of) relativistic effects. In addition, we present fundamental insights into pump-probe X-ray transient absorption processes, utilizing the relativistic real-time electron dynamics. We demonstrate how the additional degrees of freedom, namely, pulse intensity, duration, frequency and time-delay between pump and probe pulses, provides extra information regarding the electronic structure and dynamics, typically absent in conventional steady-state experiments.

Calculation of Breit and QED effects using Gaussian spinor basis functions

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The relativistic molecular electronic structure program *BERTHA* [1,2] employs a Gaussian spinor basis set and computational methods based on the explicit representation of the relativistic charge-current density, j^μ . In this presentation, we discuss recent progress in including the low-frequency form of the Breit interaction in molecular structure calculations, revealing the dominant role played by one-centre contributions that may be evaluated efficiently using the Racah methods of atomic physics [3]. The application of these methods to the evaluation of *PT*-odd effects in thallium fluoride and their extension to the evaluation of matrix elements of the frequency-dependent transverse interaction are also discussed.

The evaluation of QED effects in electronic structure calculations, such as vacuum polarization and the electron self-energy, is usually accommodated using effective potentials. Here, we present alternative approaches that build on earlier work [4,5]. The first is based on representations of the renormalized vacuum charge density, which facilitates the evaluation of vacuum polarization effects using familiar Gaussian integral technologies. In the second approach, we utilize four-component Gaussian spinor basis functions that satisfy charge conjugation symmetry by construction [6,7]. We show that *ab initio* calculations of vacuum polarization that employ this basis set satisfy Furry's Theorem and reproduce benchmark calculations of the higher-order vacuum polarization in atoms, without the use of any regularization [7]. The existing charge-current integral technologies of *BERTHA* and conventional approaches to the relativistic many-body problem are readily adapted to this new basis set.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. M. Quiney, H. Skaane, I. P. Grant, *Adv. Quant. Chem.*, **32**, 1-49 (1998).
- [2] L. Belpassi, M. de Santis, H. M. Quiney, F. Tarantelli, L. J. Storchi, *J. Chem. Phys.*, **152**, 164118 (2020).
- [3] I. P. Grant, *Relativistic Quantum Theory of Atoms and Molecules*, (Springer Science and Business Media, LLC, 2007).
- [4] H. M. Quiney and I. P. Grant, *J. Phys. B: At. Mol. Opt. Phys.*, **27**, L299-L304 (1994).
- [5] H. Persson, I. Lindgren, S. Salomonsson, P. Sunnergren, *Phys. Rev. A*, **48**, 2772-2778 (1993).
- [6] M. Salman and T. Saue, *Symmetry*, **12**, 1121 (2020).
- [7] H. M. Quiney and I. P. Grant, *Atoms*, (submitted, 2022).

Basis Sets for Relativistic Atomic and Molecular Calculations

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This presentation reviews the development and choice of Gaussian basis sets for relativistic atomic and molecular calculations. The discussion includes requirements for SCF, correlation, and polarization functions; symmetry requirements; issues with contracted functions; determination of exponents; and implications for efficient coding of integrals. Further information can be found in an upcoming review [1].

References

[1] K. G. Dyall, Basis sets for relativistic molecular calculations, in: *Comprehensive Computational Chemistry*, ed. R. Boyd and M. Yanez, (Elsevier: 2022), submitted.

Vacuum polarization in the finite basis problem

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In 1928 Paul Dirac came up with a precise relativistic quantum theory that predicted (in a natural way) the fine-structure splitting, the electron magnetic moment, and other fine details of the hydrogen problem. A few years later, precise experimental measurements were able to show that the Dirac theory fails to explain subtler details: the Lamb shift energy splitting, the electron anomalous magnetic moment, the hyperfine splitting, and other delicate hydrogenic details. It was later shown that this discrepancy can be, to a large extent, explained by the Quantum ElectroDynamics (QED) theory. In the framework of the QED perturbation theory, the first-order (dominant) radiative correction yields the vacuum polarization (VP) (fig. 1a), and the self-energy (SE) processes (fig. 1b).

Figure 1: The lowest-order (e^2) one-electron radiative correction processes.

In order to account for these QED effects in practical calculations, several effective potentials (Hamiltonians) were derived/constructed. The main downsides of these potentials are: 1) the SE potentials are parameterized to reproduce the "exact" energy-shifts [1,2] and 2) the $(\alpha Z)^{n>1}$ VP potentials require the evaluation of numerically expensive integrals (see [3]). To overcome these two limitations, we propose to work in the framework of the finite basis approximation of the Dirac equation and build these QED quantities from the numerically calculated solutions. We have first decided to consider the VP problem for practical reasons: 1) its locality and 2) the availability of the precise effective VP potentials. Using complex analysis techniques, we have derived the mathematical expressions of the VP density: the electron-positron cloud that screens the electron-nucleus interaction, for arbitrary order $n \geq 0$ in the $(\alpha Z)^n$ -expansion. These expressions can be directly employed in practical numerical calculation. In addition, we have shown that in the case where the basis set is invariant under charge conjugation symmetry, our results were in line with the Furry theorem [4]. Finally, we have shown that using this symmetric basis, the higher-order $n > 1$ VP density can be efficiently calculated, and the obtained results are in great agreement with the more sophisticated computations (as done in [3]).

References

- [1] Flambaum and Ginges. 2005. *Physical Review A*, 72(5), p.052115.
- [2] Shabaev, Tupitsyn, and Yerokhin. 2013. *Physical Review A*, 88(1), p.012513.
- [3] Mohr, Plunien, and Soff. 1998. *Physics Reports*, 293(5-6), pp.227-369.
- [4] Furry. 1937. *Physical Review*, 51(2), p.125.

Spin Current Density Functional Theory (SCDFT) for Solids Made Practical: The Interplay of Spin-Orbit Coupling and Fock Exchange

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The self-consistent treatment of spin-orbit coupling (SOC) is presented, as recently implemented in the CRYSTAL program for quantum-mechanical simulations of materials, within a two-component ($2c$) spinor approach [1]. The fundamental role of non-local exact Fock exchange is highlighted in the framework of the spin current density functional theory (SCDFT) [2-5]. We show how standard “hybrid” exchange-correlation functionals (i.e. including a fraction α of Fock exchange) allow for practical SCDFT calculations with SOC through a proper orbital relaxation of current densities (orbital and spin).

Weyl fermions are massless solutions of the Dirac equation described by $2c$ complex spinors. Such elusive objects emerge as quasi-particles in so-called Weyl semi-metals (WSM) [6-7]. We apply DFT and SCDFT to the characterization of the electronic properties of TaAs, a Weyl semi-metal and show how an SCDFT formulation is essential to a correct quantitative description of its electronic features [8].

Figure 1 Electronic structure of TaAs WSM upon treatment of SOC within the SCDFT versus standard DFT.

References

- [1] J.K. Desmarais, J-P. Flament and A. Erba, *Phys. Rev. B* (2020), 101, 235142.
- [2] G. Vignale and M. Rasolt, *Phys. Rev. B* (1988), 37, 10685.
- [3] K. Bencheikh, *J. Phys. A* (2003), 36, 11929.
- [4] J.K. Desmarais, J-P. Flament and A. Erba, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* (2019), 10, 3580.
- [5] J.K. Desmarais, J-P. Flament and A. Erba, *Phys. Rev. B* (2020), 102, 235118.
- [6] H. Weyl, *Z. Phys.* (1929), 56, 330.
- [7] S.-M. Huang, S.-Y. Xu, I. Belopolski et al., *Nat. Commun.* (2015), 6, 7373.
- [8] F. Bodo, J.K. Desmarais and A. Erba, *Phys. Rev. B* (2022), 105, 125108.

Efficient all-electron four-component Kohn–Sham theory for relativistic band structures and properties of periodic solids

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First-principles studies of electronic structure and properties of materials in solid state are computationally very demanding due to the infinite nature of periodic systems. Already for density functional theory (DFT), its straightforward extension from molecules to solids cannot be used to simulate materials with existing supercomputer machines. This complication is even more apparent for materials containing heavy elements where the fully relativistic treatment using a multicomponent Hamiltonian and the variational spin–orbit coupling is mandatory. To reduce the computational cost, common approaches employ pseudopotentials, muffin-tin approximation, approximate two-component Hamiltonians, or include spin–orbit coupling only within the muffin-tin radius or as a perturbation.

Aiming for an efficient and stable method that leverages existing quantum-chemistry technologies and is capable of predicting properties of solids that contain elements across the entire periodic table while treating core and valence states on equal footing, we developed an all-electron four-component method using Gaussian-type orbitals [1] and implemented it in the RESPECT code [2,3]. In the talk, I will present recent advancements, such as the resolution-of-the-identity approach, the fast multipole method for the lattice summations of the Coulomb interactions, and show how an orthonormal basis in momentum space is constructed in the four-component setting. These improvements were necessary for high quality results of 2D transition metal dichalcogenides [4] (TMDs) exhibiting strong spin–orbit coupling and enable large-scale calculations of materials containing heavy atoms in the simulation supercell without concern about the computational or memory costs. The robustness of the technology will be demonstrated on the basis set convergence of relativistic band structures of TMDs employing all-electron bases with diffuse functions included.

References

- [1] M. Kadek, M. Repisky, and K. Ruud, *Phys. Rev. B* (2019), 99, 205103.
- [2] M. Repisky, S. Komorovsky, M. Kadek, *et al.*, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2020), 152, 184101.
- [3] www.respectprogram.org
- [4] M. Kadek, B. Wang, M. Joosten, *et al.* (in prep.)

Relativistic Effects in Large, Complex Systems in an All-Electron Framework Based on Numeric Atom-Centered Basis Sets

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This talk discusses the implementation of relativistic electronic structure theory in the FHI-aims code [1], a high-precision, general-purpose electronic structure package covering non-periodic systems (molecules, clusters) as well as periodic systems (solids, surfaces, nanostructures) on equal footing. We discuss the implementation of a quasi-four-component (Q4C) approach [2] that utilizes the shape of numerically tabulated, atom-centered orbitals for an efficient basis set representation of the Dirac-Coulomb Hamiltonian based on density-functional theory (DFT). Efficient numerical integrals of the Hamiltonian are obtained by exploiting error cancellation between atomic solutions (obtained on a dense logarithmic grid) and the actual numerical Hamiltonian matrix elements, integrated using the traditional, much sparser Becke-type overlapping atom-centered integration grids of quantum chemistry. Extensive benchmarks demonstrate the precision of the approach, including binding energy curves of dimers, equations of state of selected solids, as well as energy band structures of 103 periodic solids, covering chemical elements from Li to Po and using the well-established linearized augmented plane-wave code Wien2k as a high-precision reference. We then compare the quality of band structures and total-energy based results to non-relativistic, scalar-relativistic (atomic zero-order regular approximation in the specific implementation in [1]) and non-selfconsistent spin-orbit coupling (n.s.c. SOC) [3] calculations on otherwise exactly equal footing. Not unexpectedly, scalar-relativistic dimer binding energies exhibit large errors for $6p$ -element based dimers (and to a lesser extent for the $5p$ dimer I_2). Similarly, energy band structures based on n.s.c. SOC show the most significant deviations from their self-consistent Q4C counterparts for systems that include $6p$ valence electrons. However, the mean deviation between n.s.c. SOC and Q4C band structures remains at a level of a few tenths of an eV at most, within the accuracy range expected from typical hybrid DFT. Given the attainable system size range of well above 1,000 atoms for n.s.c. spin-orbit coupled hybrid DFT in FHI-aims, this approach remains highly attractive for energy band structure calculations of large, complex solids and nanostructures including heavy elements. We demonstrate the usefulness of the approach by discussing spin-splitting effects [4,5] in the energy band structures of lead-halide based, crystalline hybrid organic-inorganic perovskites with chiral organic functionality, a promising platform to implement spin transport effects and chiroptical effects in complex, tunable semiconductors.

References

- [1] V. Blum *et al.*, *Comp. Phys. Commun.* (2009), 180, 2175-2196.
- [2] R. Zhao *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. B* (2021), 103, 245144.
- [3] W.P. Huhn, V. Blum, *Phys. Rev. Materials* (2017), 1, 033803.
- [4] M.K. Jana *et al.*, *Nature Communications* (2020), 11, 4699.
- [5] M.K. Jana *et al.*, *Nature Communications* (2021), 12, 4982.

Modelling of Spin-Orbit Coupling Effects in Ferroelectrics

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During the last couple of decades, the spin-orbit interaction has played an increasingly crucial role in solid state physics, thanks to its relevance as a rich microscopic mechanism from the fundamental point of view and as a driving force for innovative spintronic applications on the technological side. After a general overview on spin-orbit coupling (SOC) in periodic crystals, I will discuss two non-trivial aspects where this relativistic interaction gives rise to novel and exotic phenomena in multifunctional materials. First, I will focus on the ab-initio modelling of (non-magnetic) ferroelectric semiconductors, where SOC leads to a tight link between Rashba spin-splitting, spin-texture and electric polarization, with the appealing perspective of electric-field control of spin-degrees of freedom and long-sought integration of spintronics with ferroelectricity. Second, I will discuss first-principles results for two-dimensional magnets, where SOC, mostly arising not from the 3d transition metal but rather from anionic p-orbitals, can play a relevant role in the emergence of multiferroicity and magnetoelectricity.

Relativistic correlated electronic structure and the calculation of accurate ground-state, core and valence properties of heavy element species

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Accurate electronic structure calculations have become an indispensable tool to understand the molecular properties of heavy and superheavy elements. Such approaches help make sense of the underlying complex physical processes probed by experiments, or in the case such experiments are unfeasible due to the heavy elements' radiotoxicity.

In this presentation I will outline our contributions to developments of coupled cluster approaches based on four-component Hamiltonians for ground-state properties as well as for valence and core excitation and ionization spectra [1-4], and their application to investigating heavy and super heavy elements [2, 3, 5].

Furthermore, I will outline how these can be combined with more approximate approaches through embedding theories [6], to enable the investigation of heavy element species in complex environments such as in solution.

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References

- [1] J. Pototschnig *et al.*, J. Chem. Theory Comput. (2021) **17**, 5509 [10.1021/acs.jctc.1c00260](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.1c00260)
- [2] X. Yuan, L. Visscher, A. S. P. Gomes, J. Chem. Phys. (in press) (2022). [10.1063/5.0087243](https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0087243)
- [3] A. Shee, T. Saue, L. Visscher, A. S. P. Gomes, J. Chem. Phys. (2018) **149**, 174113 [10.1063/1.5053846](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5053846)
- [4] L. Halbert, M. L. Vidal, A. Shee, S. Coriani, A. S. P. Gomes, J. Chem. Theory Comput. (2021) **17**, 3583 [10.1021/acs.jctc.0c01203](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.0c01203)
- [5] S. Kervazo, F. Réal, F. Virot, A. S. P. Gomes, V. Vallet, Inorg. Chem. (2019) **58**, 14507 [10.1021/acs.inorgchem.9b02096](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.inorgchem.9b02096)
- [6] Y. Bouchafra, A. Shee, F. Réal, V. Vallet, A. S. P. Gomes, Phys. Rev. Lett. (2018) **121**, 266001 [10.1103/PhysRevLett.121.266001](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.121.266001)

Analytic gradient techniques for spinor-based relativistic coupled-cluster theory

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We present development of analytic gradients for spinor-based relativistic coupled-cluster (CC) methods [1,2] with relativistic effects treated using an atomic mean-field approach within the exact two-component theory based on the Dirac-Coulomb-Breit Hamiltonian (the X2CAMF scheme) [3,4]. The usefulness of analytic relativistic CC gradients is demonstrated using representative applications to actinide spectroscopy [4], time-reversal symmetry-violating sensitivity parameters [5], and laser cooling of heavy-atom-containing polyatomic molecules [6].

[1] X. Zheng, C. Zhang, J. Liu, L. Cheng *J. Chem. Phys.* **156**, 151101 (2022).

[2] J. Liu, X. Zheng, A. Asthana, C. Zhang, and L. Cheng *J. Chem. Phys.* **154**, 064110 (2021).

[3] C. Zhang and L. Cheng *J. Phys. Chem. A* under review (2022).

[4] J. Liu, L. Cheng *J. Chem. Phys.* **148**, 144108 (2018).

[5] C. Zhang, X. Zheng, and L. Cheng *Phys. Rev. A* **104**, 012814 (2021).

[6] C. Zhang, B. L. Augenbraun, Z. D. Lasner, N. B. Vilas, J. M. Doyle, and L. Cheng *J. Chem. Phys.* **155**, 091101 (2021).

Four-Component Relativistic Multireference Methods: Find the Balance between Relativistic Effects and Electron Correlation

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The accurate description of electronic properties of heavy-elements and their molecular complexes requires an electronic structure method be able to treat both relativistic and electron correlation (both static and dynamic) effects on an equal footing. On the one hand, relativistic effects, including both scalar relativities and spin-couplings, give rise to unique chemical reactivities, magnetic properties, and optical responses of heavy-element compounds. On the other, highly degenerate outer-shells of late-row elements require a multi-configurational method that incorporates important electron correlations in the underlying electronic structure theory. In this talk, electronic structure properties of heavy element complexes are discussed in the context of the variational relativistic four-component multi-reference electronic structure framework. Particularly, emphases will be placed on how different orbital shells are involved in different types of electron correlation and how they affect the ground state energy and fine structure splittings.

PROGRAM

REHE 2022

DAY 5

SEPTEMBER 30

INVITED TALKS SESSION 13

From 09:00 to 11:00

CONCLUDING REMARKS

From 11:00 to 11:15

LIGHT LUNCH

From 11:15 to 12:00

INVITED TALKS

ABSTRACT

DAY 5

SEPTEMBER 30

WENJIAN LIU

"SOiCI: Combining iCI with SOC for Fine Structures of Heavy Systems"

LUKAS KONECNY

"Linear Response in Relativistic Quantum-Electrodynamical Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory"

ALEKSANDRA A. KYUBERIS

"Theoretical study of properties of radioactive molecules"

ILYA I. TUPITSYN

"Specific features of electronic structure and chemical properties of super-heavy elements of the 7th and 8th periods"

SOiCI: Combining iCI with SOC for Fine Structures of Heavy Systems

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The iterative configuration interaction (iCI) approach[1], an iterative realization of the static-dynamic-static (SDS) Ansatz for parametrizing many-electron wave functions[2], is an exact full CI solver by constructing and diagonalizing a $3N_p$ -by- $3N_p$ matrix in each iteration and converges monotonically from above to the exact $3N_p$ roots, no matter how many electrons and orbitals are to be correlated. When combined with the selection of configuration for static correlation and the perturbative treatment of dynamic correlation, the resulting iCIPT2[3,4] becomes near exact for strongly correlated systems. The underlying tabulated unitary group approach (TUGA)[3] for the evaluation and reuse of basic coupling coefficients between randomly selected configuration state functions facilitate the extension of iCI/iCIPT2 to the treatment of spin-orbit coupling, leading to SOiCI[5]. Spin orbital relaxations can further be accounted for self-consistently by optimizing the SOiCI wave function with respect to orbital rotations, leading to SOiCISCF[6]. Both binary double group and time reversal symmetries can be used to facilitate the SOiCI and SOiCISCF calculations and the state assignment.

References:

1. W. Liu and M. R. Hoffmann, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 12, 1169 (2016).
2. W. Liu and M. R. Hoffmann, *Theor. Chem. Acc.* 133, 1481 (2014).
3. N. Zhang, W. Liu, and M. R. Hoffmann, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 16, 2296 (2020).
4. N. Zhang, W. Liu, and M. R. Hoffmann, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 17, 949 (2021).
5. N. Zhang, Y. Xiao, and W. Liu, *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* 34, 224007 (2022).
6. Y. Guo, N. Zhang, and W. Liu (to be published).

Linear Response in Relativistic Quantum-Electrodynamical Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory

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Recent experimental advances in polaritonic chemistry, nanoplasmonics and solid-state physics allowed to explore the interaction of light and matter in the strong coupling regime [1]. The strong coupling necessitates quantized description of the electromagnetic field such as cavity modes inside an optical cavity. The theoretical framework of choice is therefore quantum electrodynamics (QED) [2, 3]. However, the state-of-the art is non-relativistic QED based on the Pauli–Fierz Hamiltonian or even more approximate models. In this work we introduce a *relativistic* quantum-electrodynamical time-dependent density functional theory (QED-TDDFT) for molecules in cavities that combines four-component Dirac–Kohn–Sham treatment of electrons with quantized description of cavity modes. We present the theoretical foundation of the developed method together with a computer implementation in the relativistic DFT program ReSpect [4]. In the benchmark calculations we examine the linear response of heavy element-containing molecules inside optical cavities.

References

- [1] M. Ruggenthaler, N. Tancogne-Dejean, J. Flick, H. Appel and A. Rubio, *Nat. Rev. Chem.* (2018), 2, 0118.
- [2] M. Ruggenthaler, F. Mackenroth and D. Bauer, *Phys. Rev. A* (2011), 84, 042107.
- [3] J. Flick, D. M. Welakuh, M. Ruggenthaler, H. Appel and A. Rubio, *ACS Photonics* (2019), 6, 2757.
- [4] M. Repisky S. Komorovsky, M. Kadek, L. Konecny, U. Ekstrom, E. Malkin, M. Kaupp, K. Ruud, O. L. Malkina and V. G. Malkin, *J. Chem. Phys.* (2020), 152, 184101.

Theoretical study of properties of radioactive molecules

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Heavy diatomic molecules are currently considered to be among the most sensitive systems used in the search for the P,T-violating effects and in probing of the Standard Model of particle physics. In certain molecules effects resulting from both parity violation and time-reversal violation (P,T - odd effects) are considerably enhanced with respect to atomic systems. The strength of these interactions grows with atomic number, nuclear spin and nuclear deformation. Molecules with atomic nuclear octupole deformation are sensitive for investigating of parity and time-reversal violating effects, in particular nuclear EDM or electric EDM. Diatomic molecules, like AcF and RaF, has been proposed to be sensitive to the various effects, for example, Schiff moment of the nucleus [1, 2]. Nowadays different laboratories plan to perform experimental study of radioactive molecules in aim to measure isotopologue shifts, hyperfine structures and so on. Pursuing studies on AcF can also provide insight into dynamics of molecular extraction of Ac, as a pathway to delivering a wider range of actinium isotopes for experiments. This work aims to determine molecular properties of the RaF and AcF at the highest possible level of computational accuracy using the couple cluster in relativistic framework. The ionization potential, excitation energies, and spectroscopic constants of AcF, RaF will be presented and the uncertainty of the predicted values will be discussed.

References

- [1] D. Cho, K. Sangster, and E. Hinds. *Phys. Rev. A*, 44:164–164, 1991.
- [2] V. Flambaum and V. Dzuba. *Phys. Rev. A*, 101:42504, 2020.

Specific features of electronic structure and chemical properties of super-heavy elements of the 7th and 8th periods

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In this work, the results of the electronic-structure calculations for a number of super-heavy elements (SHE) of the 7th and 8th periods with atomic numbers $Z = 111-170$ and their lighter homologues are presented [1,2]. For a number of the 7th and 8th period elements, various chemical properties such as ionization potentials, electron affinities, root mean square radii and widths of the electron-density distribution of valence shells are calculated. Moreover, the relativistic electron localization functions (RELF) and Shannon entropy, which both characterize the degree of localization of electrons in atom are evaluated. Quantum electrodynamical (QED) corrections are calculated as well. Based on the obtained results, the role of the relativistic and QED effects on the electronic structures of SHEs was analyzed, and conclusions about the extension of the Mendeleev's periodic law to the region of SHEs were drawn. However, the electronic structure of SHEs is unique in several aspects:

(i) Spin-orbital splitting of valence p -shells reaches up about 10 eV in Og ($Z=118$) and about 400 eV in element with atomic number $Z=165$. In addition, for $Z=165$ element, the spin-orbital splitting of the core $2p$ shell is extremely large and is about 325 keV. As a result, due to the strong relativistic contraction, the radial distribution of the electron density of the valence $p_{1/2}$ -shell starts to overlap with the outer core shells and RELF is close to 0.5 in the valence region. In Ref. [3], this effect in Og was interpreted as smearing out the valence electron density distribution and its approaching to the case of the homogeneous electron gas. A similar effect is observed for the strongly-bound core shells in element with $Z = 165$. In this case, the electron densities of the $1s$ - and $2p_{1/2}$ - shells begin to overlap and the RELF value becomes close to 0.5. However, this behavior of the electron density in the core region cannot indicate that it is close to a homogeneous electron gas.

(ii) Starting from the $Z = 125$ element, the $5g$ -shell with the large angular momentum ($l = 4$) is occupied with electrons. The effective radial potential for the $5g$ -electron, which includes a large centrifugal repulsive term, has two potential wells which lead to the so-called orbital collapse. In this case, the problem of understanding the meaning of the numerical solutions, and the physical origin of the transition between these two wells arises. The orbital collapse is also observed for the f -electrons in rare- earth elements [4].

References

- [1] M. Y. Kaygorodov, L. V. Skripnikov, I. I. Tupitsyn, E. Eliav, Y. S. Kozhedub *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. A*, **104**, 012819 (2021).
- [2] I. I. Tupitsyn, A. V. Malyshev, D. A. Glazov, M. Y. Kaygorodov, Y. S. Kozhedub, *etal.*, *Opt. Spectr.* **129**, 1038 (2021).
- [3] P. Jerabek, B. Schuetrumpf, P. Schwerdtfeger, and W. Nazarewicz, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **120**, 053001 (2018).
- [4] J.-R. Connerade and R.C. Kamatak, *Handbook on the Physics and Chemistry of Rare Earths*, v. 28, p. 1 (2000).